

Master Thesis

Business Model Innovation Based on New Product Development in Small and Medium- Sized German IT Service Companies

Applicability and tailoring of the industry standard frameworks

**Master thesis for the award of the academic degree of
Master of Business Administration at FH Burgenland**

Alexander Dolgopolskiy

2230018010

Academic Supervisor: Dr. rer. nat. Lisa C. Badstieber B.Sc., M.Sc., MBA

Date of submission: 01.10.2024

Email: dolgopolsky.a@gmail.com

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/alexander-dolgopolskiy>

I hereby declare on oath that I have written this thesis independently and without the aid of any unauthorized help and that I have not used any sources other than those indicated. All passages taken verbatim or in spirit from the sources cited are marked as such.

If the Master thesis involves the use of tools (in particular IT- and AI-supported tools), I declare that I have listed them in full in the thesis with the respective product name, the product version and a description of the range of functions used.

I also declare that I have written this thesis in accordance with the applicable examination regulations of the FH Burgenland and the guidelines of the Austrian Agency for Research Integrity on good scientific practice (<https://oeawi.at/richtlinien/>). The thesis has not been submitted for review or assessment in Austria or abroad and has not been published.*

Stuttgart, 01.10.2024

Place and date

handwritten signature**

*At the time of submission, this thesis had not been published.

**The thesis was submitted with a signature, which was removed for publication.

Abstract

In recent years, the German economy has been affected by several geopolitical factors. The consequences of the latter, in combination with other macroeconomic and technology-related trends, are having a multilateral impact on German IT services and consulting companies, which are classified as small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The purpose of this thesis was to analyze New Product Development (NPD) based Business Model Innovation (BMI) within this group of companies as one of the approaches to ensure sustainability and resilience in the current market dynamics.

Through a literature review, we characterized the market dynamics and NPD-based BMI as a business strategy. Then, using industry-standard frameworks and methodologies, we identified the capabilities that are expected to be developed in the target group of companies to successfully implement this BMI. We conducted ten in-depth interviews with the target SMEs, their customers, and their consultants to validate our theoretical findings with first-hand, real-world market perspectives.

Based on the insights gained from these steps, we summarized the key factors to consider when implementing NPD-based BMI in SMEs of the target group and the most important success factors. Finally, we elaborated general suggestions for tailoring the industry-standard frameworks and methodologies to the requirements of NPD-based BMI at German IT service and consulting SMEs to ensure long-term success and achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Keywords: new product development, business model innovation, business strategy, digital products, product management, software engineering

Preface

This master's thesis is the culmination of two years of MBA studies at the FH Burgenland, as well as the new responsibilities that my employer, the evia Group, entrusted to me around the same time. And finally, all of this was made possible by our family's move to Germany exactly 10 years ago as I write this. It has been and continues to be a fascinating professional and personal journey.

Although this master's thesis is a very modest contribution from a scientific point of view, it is a very big step for me personally, and I'd like to express my deepest gratitude to everyone who has supported me, directly or indirectly. I would like to mention some of these people and organizations personally and apologize to those I have unintentionally forgotten to mention.

First of all, I would like to thank my family and especially my beloved wife Tatiana for all their understanding and support during these years of sitting and studying in the evenings and weekends.

I would like to thank my employer evia Gruppe for sponsoring my MBA studies and providing me with the relevant challenging tasks and continuous learning opportunities. I would like to thank WBS AKADEMIE and personally i. A. Mag. Christian Kupetz, FH Burgenland and personally Walter Hölblinger, MBA, as well as all our lecturers and the administration for the excellent opportunity to study IT-Management remotely in an excellently organized MBA course with a unique "metaverse" learning experience.

I would like to thank my academic supervisor Dr. Lisa C. Badstieber for her friendly and professional support, guidance and patience.

Last but not least, I would like to thank all the interviewees who took the time to provide me with the most interesting and important insights that made this work meaningful, enjoyable and worthwhile. We are all partners in sustainable development.

And, of course, my heartfelt thanks to Germany, our new and welcoming home, and to Austria, where I have found my alma mater, University of Applied Sciences Burgenland.

Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	1
1.1	Problem description.....	2
1.2	Research Questions.....	4
1.3	Methodology.....	4
2	Terms, Definitions and Concepts	6
2.1	Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)	6
2.2	Business Model (BM)	6
2.3	Business Model Innovation (BMI).....	12
2.4	BMI, Agility, Capabilities	16
2.4.1	Enterprise architecture (EA) related capabilities	18
2.4.2	Product, service and project management related capabilities	27
2.4.3	General (supporting) capabilities.....	31
3	Expert Interviews.....	32
3.1	The methodology and the approach.....	32
3.2	Questions to the SME management.....	33
3.3	Questions to Business consulting companies and/or individual consultants	34
3.4	Questions to the Customers of the B2B products	35
3.5	The interviewees	35
3.5.1	Categorization by business type	36
3.5.2	Categorization by geography	36
3.5.3	Categorization by business role	37
3.5.4	Demography.....	37
3.6	Discussion.....	38
3.6.1	The market pressure on the German IT-Service SMEs	38
3.6.2	What was the trigger for the NPD-based BMI	45
3.6.3	Capabilities: sensing market changes, enterprise and organizational agility, enabling BMI	48
3.6.4	Capabilities: designing new BMs.....	52
3.6.5	Capabilities: portfolio management.....	57
3.6.6	Capabilities: Product, service and project management	58
3.6.7	Capabilities: Prototyping, MVPing, Validated learning	63
3.6.8	Capabilities: General supporting capabilities	66

4	Analysis and outcomes.....	68
4.1.1	Factors to consider.....	68
4.1.2	Success factors and capabilities	71
4.1.3	Capabilities. Maturity levels.....	76
4.1.4	Tailoring the industry standard frameworks	77
5	Further research.....	84
6	Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	85
7	Literature	86
8	Expert Interviews (Attachements).....	92
9	Use of AI-based tools	93

Abbreviations

ADM	Architecture development method	I&T	Information and technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence	IT	Information technology
ART	Agile release team	ITSM	IT service management
BA	Business architecture	KPI	Key performance indicator
BAU	Business as usual	LPM	Lean portfolio management
BC	Business capability	MVP	Minimum viable product
BM	Business model	NPD	New product development
BMI	Business model innovation	OEM	Original equipment manufacturer
BMR	Business model reconfiguration	OS	Operating system
BSC	Balanced scorecard	PaaS	Platform as a service
CEC	Commission of the European Communities	POC	Proof of concept
CEO	Chief Executive Officer	R&D	Research and development
CMMI	Capability Maturity Model Integration	ROI	Return on investment
CRM	Customer relations management	SaaS	Software as a service
CSF	Critical success factor	SDG	Sustainable development goals
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid	SEO	Search engine optimization
EA	Enterprise architecture	SLA	Service level agreement
EAM	Enterprise architecture management	SME	Small and medium-size enterprise
ERP	Enterprise resources management	SVC	Service value chain
EU	European Union	TPS	Toyota Production System

Illustrations

Figure 1. Convergence of the three basic BM concepts with time 7

Figure 2. BM is part of the strategy to convert a vision into a product 8

Figure 3. Business Model Canvas 8

Figure 4. Lean Model Canvas..... 9

Figure 5. Business case through the project lifecycle 9

Figure 6. Skills and Competences relevant for the
Managed Innovation Objective of the COBIT® 2019 Framework 12

Figure 7. Relationship between BMR breadth and Tobin’s Q growth by past
profitability 13

Figure 8. Business model constituent elements changed..... 14

Figure 9. Business model innovation framework by Ramdani et al. 15

Figure 10. The four dimensions of service management of the ITIL® 4 framework.. 15

Figure 11. SAFe Core Competences..... 17

Figure 12. SAFe Core Competences..... 19

Figure 13. Business Capability Management and the TOGAF 10 framework..... 20

Figure 14. TOGAF Architecture Development Method (ADM)..... 21

Figure 15. COBIT 2019 Mapping Table: Alignment Goals—Governance and
Management Objectives 22

Figure 16. The SAFe Portfolio Canvas, adapted from The Business
Model Canvas..... 23

Figure 17. The ITIL service value chain..... 24

Figure 18. SAFe Lean Portfolio Management..... 25

Figure 19. Portfolio and Program Management in PRINCE2 (7) 26

Figure 20. The Lean Startup Build-Measure-Learn Loop 28

Figure 21. The PRINCE2 7 Plan-do-check-act cycle..... 29

Figure 22. Interviewed companies by category 36

Figure 23. Interviewed companies by the federal state of the headquarters 37

Figure 24. Interviewed professionals by business role 37

Figure 25. Interviewed professionals by business role 38

Figure 26. If there was a significant rise in market pressure on the SMEs in the previous 3-5 years 38

Figure 27. What was the trigger to start product-based BMI?..... 45

Figure 28. Organizational structures for the identification of candidate product-based BMs 49

Figure 29. Use of formalized business models at the start 52

Figure 30. Mission- and KPI-based Controlling 55

Figure 31. Market segmentation by the prevailing type of customers and the category of provided services 68

Figure 32. Investment strategy, sourcing of the product ideas, sales and marketing 70

Figure 33. EAM-related capabilities mapping 72

Figure 34. Creation, integration and management of BMs capabilities mapping 73

Figure 35. Prototyping, MVP development and validation capabilities mapping..... 73

Figure 36. Service management capability mapping 74

Figure 37. Marketing and Sales Mapping 75

Figure 38. Capability Maturity Model Integration® (CMMI)-based process-capability scheme 76

Figure 39. Combining PRINCE2 and Lean Startup 82

Tables

Table 1. A non-exhaustive list of Enterprise Architecture related Capabilities, relevant for the NPD-based BMI.....	27
Table 2. Factors and trends, constituting the market pressure on the German mid-size IT-service (individual corporate software development and consulting) segment.....	44
Table 3. Rationale for NPD-based BMIs for segments affected and unaffected by macroeconomic market pressures	69
Table 4. Successful idea sourcing and product marketing strategies for the NPD-based BMI	71
Table 5. Capability maturity levels	77

1 Introduction

About ten years ago, Steve Ballmer, the former CEO of Microsoft, gave an interview to the renowned American journalist Charlie Rose shortly after leaving his position at the software giant. Explaining why Microsoft had not entered the mobile phone race in time to compete with Apple and Samsung, he said that Microsoft's "formula" as a "software company" was working pretty well at the time, while changing strategy to include the hardware part sounded like changing religion (Charlie Rose, 2014). Microsoft's next CEO, Satya Nadella, effectively completed this move with Microsoft Azure, and recently added AI to the new formula with great success. Microsoft eventually reached a market capitalization of \$3 billion by early 2024, outperforming Apple by this measure (Randewich, 2024).

The above interview was cited in a book on the Lean Startup methodology, "The Corporate Startup: How established companies can develop successful innovation ecosystems" by Viki et al. It illustrates the idea of what the authors call "the disadvantage of incumbency". The point here is that most successful large companies are so focused on their current "cash cow products" generating high revenues that this can create blind spots in terms of monitoring the need for [disruptive] innovation. Some of these established companies (incumbents) manage to recover from the consequences, such as Microsoft. Others, such as Nokia, virtually disappear. Thus, every established "contemporary company" needs to maintain an innovation portfolio of startup-like products that explore new business models alongside the established "cash cow products" (Viki et al., 2019, pp. 14-17).

During the prosperous pre-pandemic decades of economic growth, many of Germany's small and medium-sized (SME) IT service providers, especially those partnering with the then booming industrial and financial sectors, effectively developed this incumbency. The provision of local custom software development resources to the DAH-based corporations was precisely the "cash cow" that effectively fenced the SMEs with this business model (BM) from the need for "business model innovation (BMI)", as it is defined in academic literature since at least 2004 (Mitchell & Bruckner Coles, 2004, p. 17). This was the status quo before the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent economic hurdles hit this sector.

The present work focuses on the challenges faced by these established but relatively resource-limited industry players as they follow the BMI path and, in particular, explore

the possibilities of new product development (NPD). We will focus on the range and maturity of the relevant capabilities, that need to be developed or enhanced on this journey, taking some of the leading industry enterprise architecture management (EAM), product development, project and service management frameworks as the baseline. We will also conduct expert interviews with the industry players to find out, to which extent our baseline is matched in practice and suggest an approach to tailoring the frameworks, based on the empirically determined critical success factors and limitations to maximize the value and boost sustainability as outcomes for the target group of businesses.

1.1 Problem description

Aggregated market figures show that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the German IT services sector and the software development industry in particular have suffered greatly under the general economic conditions of the pandemic and post-pandemic years (European Commission. Joint Research Centre & European Commission. Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, 2023; Federal Statistical Office (Destatis), 2023). The number of SMEs in Germany decreased by 5.1% and the number of employees by 9.6% between 2019 and 2023. The nominal value added of SMEs in Germany increased by only 10.6% over the same period, well below the rate of inflation. Adjusted for inflation, SME value added in Germany was -5.4% in 2022 compared to 2020. Firms in the services sector were the hardest hit. This is particularly true for companies that have not been able to pass on increased costs to their customers (European Commission. Joint Research Centre & European Commission. Directorate General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, 2023).

This is particularly true for IT services and software publishing (excluding computer games). With an inflation rate of +7.9% in 2022, prices for IT services rose by only 0.9% overall and for software publishing by 3.3% (Federal Statistical Office (Destatis), 2023).

For SMEs that provide custom software development and maintenance as a service to large industrial customers, the problems mentioned above coincide with another trend that was already underway before the pandemic. Advances in digital technologies and their role in the core business are forcing industrial customers, such

as car manufacturers, to insource IT services and partner with Big Tech (Felser & Wynn, 2023, S. 180, 184).

Although affected SMEs are taking a variety of approaches to cope with the rapid economic downturn, one of the most effective approaches is not only to deal with the direct impact of (pandemic) risks, but also to focus on strategy as a central business function and the development and transformation of capabilities. In particular, this includes changing or optimizing and adapting business models (BM), otherwise known as BM innovation (BMI), which is one of the key research topics in this area (Erdiaw-Kwasie et al., 2023, pp. 6,7). And one of the most effective strategies in this context is consists in building NPD capabilities and associated knowledge management practices that benefit SMEs through organizational learning, improved customer interaction, innovation, higher profits, improved operations and faster decision making (Idrees et al., 2023, p. 8). At the same time, scientific research shows, that even with numerous available process models for NPD, SMEs still struggle to find the right approach (Iqbal & Suzianti, 2021, p. 9).

When we talk about NPD-based BMI in this context, we are referring primarily to software and services that are not initially commissioned by a large customer but are offered to the general market. However, this is a major challenge for traditional service- and consulting-oriented SMEs that do not have NPD capability as part of their business architecture. Among other things, there is a lack of formalized and established processes, resources, governance, risk management practices, etc. (Iqbal & Suzianti, 2021, p. 11).

However, it is precisely organizational and strategic factors, such as the firm's innovation strategy and the way it makes decisions about R&D investments, as well as the innovation climate, culture and management practices, that form the main group of critical success factors (CSFs) for the success of NPD-based BMs (Cooper, 2019, pp. 36, 43).

In this context, one of the recommended research topics is to investigate how cause-based product innovation processes (causation, e.g. traditional project management) can be integrated with more common for SMEs 'effective' approaches (e.g. Lean Startup) (Berends et al., 2014, p. 34).

From this standpoint, the scientific contribution of the present work will consist in the theoretical and empirical gap analysis with regard to the capabilities for the NPD-based BMI at the German SMEs of the discussed group, the analysis of the way to address

this gap and the drafting of the approach to tailor the applicable industry standard EAM, governance, product and project management frameworks. We will also discuss the possible topics of further research.

1.2 Research Questions

1. What specific factors (market-related, organizational, cultural, etc.) and capabilities should German IT service SMEs consider when planning and implementing NPD-based BMI, and what are the critical success factors?
2. Based on the above factors, what would be an approach for tailoring industry standard methodologies and frameworks in the area of EAM and product management that could be systematically applied by industry players to create value and achieve the desired sustainability?

1.3 Methodology

In order to obtain answers to the above research questions and to achieve the research objective with reliable results, it is essential to use both first-hand market knowledge of IT service and consulting SMEs and other potential stakeholders, and the available literature, including documentation of industry standard methodologies and frameworks, as well as academic studies on the subject.

The first part of the present work consists of a systematic literature review following the methodology of Bortz and Döring (Döring, Bortz, 2016). The main research question is related to the scope of capabilities that are expected to be developed or adapted by SMEs for successful NPD-based BMI. The range of sources include both scientific research papers and the documentation of the relevant industry frameworks and methodologies. The first category provides us with an analysis of the current practice in the field of BMI, while the second serves as a baseline for the industry standard approach to the development and realization of capabilities.

The results of the literature review will be used to prepare the expert interviews, which are essential to gain first-hand knowledge of the specifics of German SMEs in the sector, their market position, their resource situation, their corporate architecture landscape, their competencies and strategies. Using Mayer's (2012) qualitative research methodology, we conducted 10 interviews with representatives of relevant

SMEs and have reached the saturation point. The SMEs interviewed are categorized according to the maturity of the NPD-based BMI and the company size to conduct a valid comparative analysis of the gained insights.

The above steps formed a solid basis for using the constructive research method to achieve the aim of the thesis. Among the most frequently used constructive methods analyzed, among others, in the work of Wilde and Hess (2007) the conceptual-deductive method was found to be the most suitable for the goals of the present master thesis. From the structured and analyzed practical-theoretical basis, we developed design concepts for tailoring the industry-standard frameworks and methodologies to facilitate NPD-based BMI and address the unique challenges and opportunities of this group of companies on their path to sustainability and resilience.

2 Terms, Definitions and Concepts

2.1 Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)

Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (formerly just small and medium-sized enterprises) as a range of companies is defined by the European Commission in terms of employee numbers and financial “ceilings” (Commission of the European Communities [CEC], 2003).

In this master thesis, we are focusing primarily on the two upper segments, namely small (10-49 employees and up to EUR 10 million turnover/balance sheet) and medium-sized (50-250 employees and up to EUR 43 million) enterprises. Our assumption was, that the micro segment (up to 9 employees) could generally not be regarded as incumbent, however one of the interviewed companies with five employees either forms a notable exception or disproves this assumption, which may constitute a subject of further scientific work.

According to the same document (CEC, 2003), an enterprise is any entity engaged in an economic activity, regardless of its legal form. This would therefore include the self-employed or freelancers, who constitute an important segment of the IT sector. However, we would stick to the SME segments mentioned above also in this respect.

2.2 Business Model (BM)

The search for a best comprehensive definition of BM started decades ago. An often-cited study by Mitchell and Coles from 2004 gives a very broad interpretation of BM as the combination of “who”, “what”, “when”, “where”, “why”, “how”, and “how much” an organization uses to provide its goods and services and develop resources to continue its efforts (Mitchell & Bruckner Coles, 2004, p.17).

Another rather abstract definition was given a few years later by Teece, one more massively referenced researcher on the subject, in who’s wording BM essentially is a conceptual, rather than financial, model of a business in the context of organizational and financial “architecture” of a business (Teece, 2010, p. 173).

Further literature reviewers on the subject generally acknowledge, that the efforts to provide a single definition of BM failed, although the conceptual understanding has

the tendency of converging with years in the direction of strategy and organization (Wirtz et al., 2016, pp. 38, 39) (See Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Convergence of the three basic BM concepts with time (source: Wirtz et al., 2016, p. 39)

This is generally confirmed by the previous prominent BM literature review by Zott et al. from 2011. The authors discovered the scientific trend to see the BM centered around a firm's revenues and costs, its value proposition to the customer and the mechanisms to capture value, rather than with technology. The technology in its turn is seen primarily as a BM enabler (Zott et al., 2011, p. 1034). The study also concludes, that conceived in this way, BM can be a vehicle for innovation as well as a subject of innovation. And this is essential for the present master thesis.

We find generally the same interpretation in the "Lean Startup" family of methodologies, having roots in lean manufacturing and bringing it in the context of entrepreneurship (Klačmer Čalopa et al., 2020, p. 277) and formalized in the iconic book by Erik Ries (Ries, 2011). According to Ries, together the BM, product road map and a point of view about partners, competitors and the customer constitute the strategy to achieve an entrepreneur's vision in form of a business product (Ries, 2011, p. 1) (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. BM is part of the strategy to convert a vision into a product (source: Ries, 2011, p. 1)

This concept gave birth to a family of methodologies and publications, in one of which Ash Maurya states, that BM is a product of its own (Maurya, 2022, p. 23). This is however no contradiction, as Maurya adapted Alexander Osterwalder’s Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010, p. 42) (see Fig. 3) to create the Lean Canvas (see Fig. 4), which is specifically tailored for startups and entrepreneurs and basically serves as the representation of the BM and includes the elements, that Ries placed within the strategy (Maurya, 2022, p. 57). Important point is that the underlying BM is expected to be dynamic, subject to continuous innovation. Maurya encourages “large companies” to get away from a single BM, taking an “ecosystem approach” to their businesses instead, which practically means building and maintaining specific business models for each business product, aligned with the company’s general strategy (Maurya, 2022, p. 17).

Figure 3. Business Model Canvas (source: Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010, p. 42)

Problem List your customers' top 3 problems	Solution Outline possible solutions for each problem	Unique value proposition Singular, clear, compelling statement that turns an unaware visitor into an interested prospect	Unfair advantage Something that can't be easily copied or bought	Customer segments List your target customers and users
Existing alternatives List how these problems are solved today	Key metrics List key numbers telling how your business is doing today	High-level concept List your X for Y analogy (e.g., YouTube = Flickr for videos)	Channels List your paths to customers	Early adopters List characteristics of your ideal customer
Cost structure List your fixed and variable costs		Revenue streams List your source of revenue		
<small>Lean Canvas is adapted from Business Model Canvas and is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Un-parted License.</small>				

Figure 4. Lean Model Canvas (source: Maurya, 2022, p. 57)

If we now turn to an established project management PRINCE2® 7 framework, we see, that its related term would be “Business Case”, which is one of the framework’s practices (PeopleCert, 2023, p.55), although business case is not a BM, but rather its projection on the project perspective. From the PRINCE2 7 framework point of view, business case is the underlying document for a project, ensuring that an organization gets value in form of benefits from the project’s products during and after the project is completed. It is used by senior management to make go/no go decisions about the project (Johanes & Arviansyah, 2021, p. 2). And alike BM, business case is constantly updated during its realization (see Fig. 5), which is implicitly looped back in the underlying BM. Important here is also, that a project is limited in time and scope, while a BM and the “business” that it refers to are not. At least not necessarily. PRINCE2® 7 framework however points at the transition from a project to the “business as usual” (BAU), when the change has been implemented by the project realization and the BAU resumes in its new form, i.e. according to an updated BM.

Figure 5. Business case through the project lifecycle (source: PeopleCert, 2023, p.61)

The TOGAF® Standard, a Standard of The Open Group organization, widely used for EAM in the industrial domain (Syamfithriani et al., 2024, p. 424), has a special Guide as a part of TOGAF® Series Guides, named “Business Models” (The Open Group, 2022a). The Guide defines BM as some form of a model, that describes the rationale for how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value. Same, as with the Business Case of PRINCE2 7, the framework does not prescribe or require a specific artefact or form, that this model needs to be represented by. The Guide accepts in principle any form, starting with an abstract concept in a leader’s mind and up to a formalized detailed artifact, such as a Business Model Canvas from Osterwalder & Pigneur and so on, defining structural elements and relationships between them.

The Guide also makes a link to the Enterprise Architecture (EA) by stating, that a purpose of BM is to establish a common understanding or alignment for the intended manipulation of the business in pursuit of new strategic alternatives, i.e. achieving business strategy, whereas EA breaks the BE down into functional elements, including the business capabilities, value streams, organizational structure, and information objects.

In this way, through business innovation via business modelling and enterprise architecture development the desired business result is achieved.

To conclude this section and considering that the focus group of this work are IT companies developing digital products, it is worth mentioning yet another popular IT governance framework COBIT 2019 (Auth & Jokisch, 2023, p. 1). COBIT 2019 references business model within its Domain “Align, Plan and Organize” and subsequently, Management Objective “APO02 — Managed Strategy”. Business model is brought up in the activities of two management practices: “APO02.01 Understand enterprise context and direction” and “APO02.03 Define target digital capabilities”. In this case, as also mentioned earlier in the referenced studies, IT is playing the role of a key enabler for the business strategy, whereby understanding the business context and targets, including through BMs, is done to determine the required IT-related capabilities, methodologies and organizational approaches required to realize the defined product and service portfolio (ISACA, 2018, p. 66).

However, what do we exactly mean by NPD-based BMs at the established IT service and consulting SMEs? On the one hand, for this group of companies, having established commissioned-project-based BMs, the development of own products for

the open market and structuring new businesses around them, is rather creation of new BMs, than adjusting the existing ones. The new products can be quite different in their nature – e.g a software as a service (SaaS) for corporate clients and a mobile application, targeted at private users. In terms of creating, delivering and capturing value, these would have quite different entries on a business model canvas, different value streams. These would also be quite different from the “mainstream” business model of an IT service provider.

So, with the NPD as the basis of new business lines, do we call it an extension of a company’s BM, or do we talk about the creation and expansion of an ecosystem of BMs hierarchically underlying the “top level business model” of the company? Practically, in terms of artefacts, the latter can be thought of as what is defined as “viewpoints” and “views” in ArchiMate® 3.2 Specification (The Open Group, 2023c). In this sense, considering (“viewing”) a specific product-based BM with its elements and value streams as a separate “BM view” would make sense to a certain combination of stakeholders and concerns (“viewpoint”), while this projected BM would still be an integral part of the overall BM of the company in terms of Enterprise Business Architecture description.

Another TOGAF Series Guide, dedicated to “Business Capabilities (BC)” further explains the framework’s standpoint on the matter (The Open Group, 2023b). According to the Guide, a company’s overarching BM is executed through the BCs, including the “individual BCs”. Whereby a task of the enterprise architecture management (EAM) is to make sure, these individual BCs are mapped back to the overarching BM, which in its turn and among other advantages ensures, that the company’s investments are aligned with the overall enterprise vision and strategy.

NPD as such is a BC in this interpretation, realized through various further capabilities, e.g. “develop business plans” or “develop business case”. NPD, as well as both other examples are part of the European classification of Skills, Competences and Occupations (ESCO), possibly the major official register of capabilities, including BCs, relevant for the present work (European Commission, 2024). In this context, BC can be generally considered a company’s business relevant “skill” and “competency”, which however requires that the company’s employees are also skilled and competent for the relevant activities.

The skill “Business plan development” is listed in the ISACA’s special guide “COBIT for Small and Medium Enterprises” for the Component “People, Skills and

Competencies” under the Management Objective “APO04 — Managed Innovation” within the “Align, Plan and Organize” Domain (ISACA, 2021, SMEs, p.86), thus linking this part of this governance framework to the subject of the current study (see Fig. 6).

D. Component: People, Skills and Competencies		
Skill	Related Guidance (Standards, Frameworks, Compliance Requirements)	Detailed Reference
Business plan development	e-Competence Framework (e-CF)—A common European Framework for ICT Professionals in all industry sectors—Part 1: Framework, 2016	A. Plan—A.3. Business Plan Development
Emerging technology monitoring	Skills Framework for the Information Age V6, 2015	EMRG
Innovating	e-Competence Framework (e-CF)—A common European Framework for ICT Professionals in all industry sectors—Part 1: Framework, 2016	A. Plan—A.9. Innovating
Innovation	Skills Framework for the Information Age V6, 2015	INOV
Research	Skills Framework for the Information Age V6, 2015	RSCH
Technology trend monitoring	e-Competence Framework (e-CF)—A common European Framework for ICT Professionals in all industry sectors—Part 1: Framework, 2016	A. Plan—A.7. Technology Trend Monitoring

Figure 6. Skills and Competences relevant for the Managed Innovation Objective of the COBIT® 2019 Framework (source: ISACA, 2021, p.86)

Before we move to the next section, let’s aggregate the outcomes of this part of literature and framework review regarding the concept of BM and the subject of the current master thesis.

Product-Based Business Model at an SME is a formalized or de-facto functioning concept of how a company is structuring and building a business product within its business ecosystem and how it delivers and captures value, associated with this product, through the relevant business capabilities, mapped back to the company’s overarching business model.

One missing element left is the definition of “value”. And, although, the primary goal of the NPD in the context of this study is to generate profit, this might not always be so straightforward in the real-life circumstances, as we will also see confirmed in the discussion section. So, let’s stick for now with the definition of value from the ITIL® 4 framework for IT service management as “the perceived benefits, usefulness, and importance of something” (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 7). ITIL, formerly known as Information Technology Infrastructure Library, is a widely accepted framework for aligning IT service with business requirements (Yu et al., 2024, p.2).

2.3 Business Model Innovation (BMI)

Among the pioneers in business model innovation research, if not the founders of the term were Donald W. Mitchell and Carol Bruckner Coles. They defined BMI as BM

replacement resulting in new product or service offerings that were not previously available, with “BM replacement” being an improvement of at least four of the elements of a BM – “who”, “what”, “when”, “where”, “why”, “how”, and “how much” (Mitchell & Bruckner Coles, 2004, p.17).

While the above definition leaves a lot of space for interpretation, the TOGAF framework tries to go more precise about it. And, although there is no direct definition of BMI in the analyzed TOGAF Series Guides and the standard itself, the guide on business models suggests, that a real BMI would be a combined shift in customer segments and value proposition, while less significant changes are considered mere BM adjustments (The Open Group, 2022a).

Both definitions make the development of NPD-based BMs at SMEs clearly a variant of BMI.

Another name for BMI and BM adjustments is “Business model reconfiguration (BMR)”, as discussed in an article by Desyllas et al., focusing on the breadth of such reconfiguration, that boosts an incumbent company’s performance through changing at least one of the elements of its BM [model] (Desyllas et al., 2022, pp. 231, 232). As a result of their research, the authors concluded that BMR is most beneficial in two cases: a) when companies with superior past performance “embark on a broad (high-risk) search for a radically different business model” and b) when companies combine high levels of [mostly technical] innovation with medium levels of BMR breadth (Desyllas et al., 2022, p. 235).

Figure 7. Relationship between BMR breadth and Tobin’s Q growth by past profitability (source: Desyllas et al., 2022, p. 254)

Figure 8. Business model constituent elements changed (source: Desyllas et al., 2022, p. 248)

These results of the study, shown on Figure 7 with the Tobin's Q (an indicator of the company's financial performance and investment potential) growth dependence on the breadth of MBR suggest that firms with previously well working BM may not benefit from BMR unless they reconfigure a broad range of their BM elements, as illustrated by Figure 8. (Desyllas et al., 2022, p. 252). The analyzed companies belonged to the "knowledge-intensive business services (KIBS)" segment, which makes it relevant for the present master thesis – the IT service and software companies, although not exclusively.

These conclusions are consistent with a recent literature review on BMI, performed by Ramdani et al. (Ramdani et al., 2019, p. 100), indicating, that, on the one hand, there are a few elements of BM, that play a key role in BMI and need to be reconfigured together in a holistic way (see Fig. 9). On the other hand, although changing only one of the elements effectively alters the whole BM, companies do profit by exploring "alternative business models through experimentation, open and disruptive innovations", thus effectively not revolutionizing, but rather expanding their overarching BM.

As we will see in the following sections of this thesis, the above conclusions are entirely consistent with the reality of the companies surveyed. In cases where multiple BM components were not reconfigured or developed, the BMs failed or incurred avoidable costs.

Figure 9. Business model innovation framework by Ramdani et al. (source: Ramdani et al., 2019, p. 94)

Here we see an important parallel with the ITIL 4 dimensions of service management (see Fig. 10), which the framework considers to be essential to consider holistically in order to ensure effective and efficient facilitation of value for customers and other stakeholders in the form of products and services (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 23)

Figure 10. The four dimensions of service management of the ITIL® 4 framework (source: Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 24)

Why are we considering service management here at all? According to ITIL 4, service is “a means of enabling value co-creation by facilitating outcomes that customers want to achieve, without the customer having to manage specific costs and risks”. In their turn, products are defined as “configurations of an organization’s resources designed to offer value for a consumer” (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 11).

Practically, especially for IT service and software companies, the output of a BM is a product, and in most cases in the form of a service. This implies that, that BMs in this domain are realized through services, hence NPD-based BMI needs to be also thought of in terms of service management, with the latter defined by the framework as “A set of specialized organizational capabilities for enabling value for customers in the form of services” (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 5).

2.4 BMI, Agility, Capabilities

What makes a company capable of achieving value through a successful BMI? In other words, how do we define BMI as an organizational capability? Is it a single or a composite, top level capability?

Not long after Womack et al. brought the Lean manufacturing principles originating from the Toyota Production System (TPS) to a wider audience (Womack et al., 1990) and a few years before the Agile Manifesto forever transformed software development and project management in the broad sense (Agile Alliance, 2001), Teece et al. outlined their “Dynamic capabilities framework” (Teece et al., 1997). After about a decade the Eric Ries joined lean and agile for the startups with his “Lean startup” methodology (Ries, E., 2011) and Dean Leffingwell generally did the same, but for the enterprise environment with his Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) with its currently latest 6.0 version released in 2023 and now also referencing the lean startup methodology (Scaled Agile Inc., 2023).

While Agile is arguably mostly famous for its “Responding to change over following a plan” principle, the lean methodology is generally associated with avoiding waste, i.e. efforts not leading to the creation of value. However, for Taiichi Ohno it was initially all about quick and adaptive changes in the production process (Womack et al., 1990, pp. 52-53). It is exactly this ability or capability to change dyes in the stamping process in the matter of minutes resulted as long ago as in 1950s in the realization of what later became famous as “fail early” – small batches of stamps could be tested quickly and

the whole process could be adjusted in case of defects, thus reducing the production waste, when scaled.

Interestingly, ITIL 4 is also lean in its core methodology, introducing “Value streams”, which, when mapped to the managed services, help identifying “non-value-adding activities”, i.e. enabling waste-elimination (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 32). And it also outlines a way of combining itself with the Agile methodology and DevOps (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 40), although indicating a risk of not complying with the “think and work holistically” principle and pointing out, that the Agile methodology needs to be applied either everywhere or nowhere. Practically, agile-lean or lean-agile is a de-facto standard for almost any modern framework in the domain we are looking at in this work, although it is out of the scope of this master thesis to prove it.

From the scientific point of view, it was exactly the now classical work of Teece et al, that formulated the set of capabilities, required for an organization to handle the change in the way, that the agile-lean frameworks suggest. The authors used the term “dynamic capabilities” to designate the rapidly changing business environment and the role of the strategic management in adjusting organizational skills, resources and functional competences to ensure continued value generation in this dynamic environment (Teece et al., 1997, p. 515). The SAFe framework names this “Business Agility”, realized through organizational competences (see Fig. 11).

Figure 11. SAFe Core Competences (source: Scaled Agile Inc., 2023)

Analyzing the Figure 11 we see, that, especially in the case of NPD as the basis of BMI, the required set of capabilities can be divided into three categories:

1. Enterprise Architecture related: capabilities, enabling the very change of BM within acceptable time to adapt to the changing environment and extract value from the opening business opportunities.
2. Product, service and project management related: capabilities, enabling product creation, delivery, continuous improvement and value capturing.
3. General (supporting) capabilities, enabling realization of the capabilities of the first two categories and not exclusively attached to the NPD.

In the context of BMI and NPD, under the term “Capability” in the present work we will understand the ability of a company to repeatedly achieve a defined output and outcome for a certain business function. This generally follows the definition of “Business capability” from the TOGAF publications (The Open Group, 2022, Business Capabilities), and the comparable definitions from the other frameworks. In line with the same mentioned TOGAF Guide, we will see a capability as realized by a combination of roles (people), processes, information, and tools.

We will also be using the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI®) of the TOGAF standard in assessing, how established a given capability is at a given company (The Open Group, 2022, Maturity Models). The CMMI model is also used by COBIT 2019 for assessing the maturity of processes (ISACA, 2018, Objectives, p. 20).

Now, let us see, which of the capabilities from each of the above categories are generally required for a structured BMI with NPD-based new BMs. It is not our goal here to fully and comparatively describe each framework’s definition of each capability, but rather to make sure, that we are in line with the selected frameworks on the scope of what’s generally required for an NPD-based BMI.

2.4.1 Enterprise architecture (EA) related capabilities

2.4.1.1 Sensing business environment changes, requiring BMI

From the Figure 11 of the SAFe framework’s Business Agility core competences, the one directly responsible for the “sensing” of the need or advantages for adapting the company’s strategy and aligning the AE architecture with it is the “Organizational agility” competence and, drilling down, the “Strategy agility” with its “Market sensing” component (Scaled Agile Inc., 2023, Organizational Agility) (see Fig. 12).

Figure 12. SAFe Core Competences (source: Scaled Agile Inc., 2023, Organizational Agility)

The same capability is mirrored in the ITIL 4 “ITIL service value system” as “Organizational agility and organizational resilience” (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 37). These are generally described as the ability of an organization to remain successful through quickly, flexibly and systematically adapting itself to the external factors. Sensing the need for a change is part of this, although the concept spans over the next capability, as well.

From the COBIT 2019 perspective, this capability is about managing the company’s strategy and aligning the governance and the processes with it. And here we have “Innovation/Differentiation” as the most relevant “Strategy Archetype”, whereby the focus is on offering different and/or innovative products and services (ISACA, 2018, Introduction and Methodology, p. 23). In the balanced scorecard (BSC) perspective of this framework, the most relevant positions would be “Product and business innovation” (EG13, Growth BSC dimension) and “Portfolio of competitive products and services” (EG01, Financial BSC dimension) (ISACA, 2018, Introduction and Methodology, p. 24).

Using the COBIT 2019 “Goals Cascade”, we come to the following result, relevant for the NPD-based BMI:

- Domain: Align, Plan and Organize
- Management Objective: AP004 – Managed Innovation
- Enterprise Goals: EG01 and EG13 (see above)

Alignment Goals:

- AG06 Agility to turn business requirements into operational solutions
- AG13 Knowledge, expertise and initiatives for business innovation

What comes down the cascade are several “management practices”, skills and business functions, mapped to the core “Components” of the COBIT 2019 framework. And, although COBIT 2019 is primarily focused on the information and technology (I&T) governance, it is applicable to our case, as a) BMI can and often is triggered by I&T and b) I&T is an indispensable component of arguably any BMI.

Consequently, among others, the following practices/skills/capabilities/business functions are listed: create an environment conducive to innovation, maintain an understanding of the enterprise environment, assess the potential of emerging technologies and innovative ideas, as well as emerging technology and technology trend monitoring, etc. (ISACA, 2018, Objectives, pp. 81 - 85). This is all about the mechanisms of triggering a BMI, so falls under this generally described capability.

As for the TOGAF framework, it “kicks-in” at a later stage, after the strategic decisions have been made, and there is a need to align the EA with them. It states, that, “Business planning at the strategy level provides the initial direction to Enterprise Architecture” and references “Business Capability Management” external framework as the input (The Open Group, 2022, The Standard, ADM, Preliminary Phase) (see Fig. 13). And eventually it also references the PRINCE2 framework for the Portfolio Management capability, which will consider further on.

Figure 13. Business Capability Management and the TOGAF 10 framework (source: The Open Group, 2022, The Standard, ADM, Preliminary Phase)

2.4.1.2 Making changes to the company's architecture, enabling BMI

This capability follows the first one in continuously assessing the existing EA as the baseline, designing the target architecture and then iteratively moving from the first one to the second. The ability to do this in a structured way is referred to as the “Enterprise Architecture Capability” in the TOFAF framework and is the first thing to evaluate in terms of maturity and build up to the required level, before moving any further (The Open Group, 2022, The Standard, ADM, Preliminary Phase).

So, in terms of TOGAF, we are talking about the Preliminary Phase of what it calls the Architecture Development Method (ADM) cycle (see Fig. 14). The ability to plan, implement and control the required AE changes, including the case of NPD-based BMI, is exactly the point of the capability for TOGAF.

Figure 14. TOGAF Architecture Development Method (ADM) (source: The Open Group, 2022, The Standard, ADM, Preliminary Phase)

It is important to mention in this context, that ADM as a method is continuously evolving with the collaborative effort of a large number of EA-practitioners (Hermawan & Sumitra, 2019, p. 4).

For COBIT 2019 “Managed Enterprise Architecture” is one of the management objectives (APO003), traced back through the Alignment goal “Agility to turn business requirements into operational solutions” (AG06) to the same Enterprise Goal EG01 – “Portfolio of competitive products and services”, as we discussed in the previous capability for sensing the need for business innovation (AG13) (ISACA, 2018, Objectives, pp. 297, 298) (see Fig.15).

		AG01 I&T compliance and support for business compliance with external laws and regulations	AG02 Managed I&T-related risk	AG03 Realized benefits from I&T-enabled investments and services portfolio	AG04 Quality of technology-related financial information	AG05 Delivery of I&T services in line with business requirements	AG06 Agility to turn business requirements into operational solutions	S in p int a
EDM01	Ensured governance framework setting and maintenance	P	S	P				
EDM02	Ensured benefits delivery			P		S	S	
EDM03	Ensured risk optimization	S	P					
EDM04	Ensured resource optimization			S		S	S	
EDM05	Ensured stakeholder engagement				S			
APO01	Managed I&T management framework	S	S	P		S		
APO02	Managed strategy			S		S	S	
APO03	Managed enterprise architecture			S		S	P	
APO04	Managed innovation			S			P	
APO05	Managed portfolio			P		P	S	

Figure 15. COBIT 2019 Mapping Table: Alignment Goals—Governance and Management Objectives (source: ISACA, 2018, Objectives, pp. 298)

In the SAFe framework, EA comes rather as an input – a link between the higher strategic levels and the system architecture, steering the agile teams, release trains and product management. However, it is a responsibility of Enterprise Architects, to foster innovative ideas and align business and technical strategies. Although there is no direct talk about exactly enabling BMI through the adjustments of AE, we may consider it implicit as a feedback loop (Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. System Architect, Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Enterprise Architect). SAFe also references TOGAF here as an external framework to deal with the EA management as such.

ITIL 4 distinguishes between Business Architecture (BA) and more service and technology related architecture types (Axelos Ltd, 2021, p. 78). BA and the architecture management in this case are about aligning the existing and target capabilities with the strategy and the needed activities to create value, performing gap analysis and overseeing the roadmap implementation. Compared with the TOGAF ADM, ITIL 4 model is more service-focused, so Service architecture is separated from Business

architecture, while Information systems architecture and Technology architecture are mappable to the according ADM phases. Interestingly, ITIL 4 also defines Environmental architecture – something, that might well also appear in a future TOGAF ADM version. ITIL 4 generally sees the above as separate architectures for bigger companies, while allowing for a “single integrated architecture” at “smaller and less complex organizations”.

Eventually, PRINCE2 7 framework does not dwell into the topic of EA, other than as a part of the “Project context” element. The cascade is from the “business management structure” through portfolio and program management to the direct subject of the framework – the project management (PeopleCert, 2023, pp. 4-8).

2.4.1.3 Enabling creation, adjustment and integration of new BMs

As the topics of BM and BMI have already been discussed above, especially in regards of TOGAF, COBIT and PRINCE2 frameworks, we will rush through this capability. In the SAFe framework, the arguably closest analogue of a BM is to be found within the Value Streams (individual BMs) represented as Value Stream Canvases, grouped into a “Portfolio” / Portfolio Canvas (Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Portfolio Vision). Here we, again find a modification of the Business Canvas as a supporting artifact (see Fig. 16).

Portfolio Canvas Portfolio Name: _____ Date: _____ Version: _____

Value Propositions						
Value Streams	Solutions	Customers	Channels	Customer Relationships	Budget	KPIs/ Revenue
Key Partners		Key Activities		Key Resources		
Cost Structure			Revenue Streams			

Figure 16. The SAFe Portfolio Canvas, adapted from The Business Model Canvas (source: Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Portfolio Vision)

The Portfolio Vision in this context can be seen as designing a Business Architecture, based on individual BMs by what SAFe calls “describing the future state of a portfolio’s value streams and solutions”.

ITIL 4 is firstly a service- (ITSM, IT service management) and not an explicitly business-oriented framework. However, as we are considering NPD-based BMI with the products in the IT domain mostly delivered in form of services, we can see a very close similarity between the concept of BM and that of ITIL’s Service Value Chain (SVC) (Axelos Ltd., 2021, p. 57) (see Fig. 17).

Figure 17. The ITIL service value chain (source: Axelos Ltd., 2021, p. 57)

ITIL 4 defines SVC as an operating model, outlining the key activities required to respond to demand by facilitating value realization, which is achieved through the creation and management of products and services. In other words, it is a realization of business and architectural agility, in relevant cases taking form of a maintained BM. Here we have a parallel with e.g. TOGAF approach, whereby BMs are included in the Architecture Vision inputs to the Business Architecture phase of the ADM to make sure the target architecture is aligned with the business strategy and its definition of value (The Open Group, 2022a).

Eventually, as discussed earlier, for the PRINCE2 framework focused on project management, Business Case can be seen as the projection of a BM on the project management perspective, serving as the basis for the continued business justification (PeopleCert, 2023, p. 70).

2.4.1.4 Creating and managing portfolios of BMI projects

In the context of NPD-Based BMI, portfolio management is first and foremost about products and services as business products. ITIL states, that the purpose of portfolio management in this respect is to ensure the right balance of these to execute the strategy of the company, considering the available resources, including funding, and eventually creating value (Axelos Ltd., 2021, p. 91). This is achieved through the application of a systematic approach, tailored for this purpose and company.

Generally, the above is common for all the discussed frameworks with some specific variations. Thus, SAFe underlines the lean approach, defining its “Lean Portfolio Management (LPM)” in case a company has several Value Streams. There can also be a number of specific portfolios aligned with different strategic themes (Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Lean Portfolio Management). LPM in this context is the business agility projection of the organizational agility (see Fig. 18).

Figure 18. SAFe Lean Portfolio Management (source: Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Lean Portfolio Management)

Lean-Agile approach is then the core of the LPM, as the budgets, products, services and projects are managed through such methodologies, as e.g. Kanban, MVP-based and generally implemented by Agile Release Teams (ART).

For the COBIT 2019 we already mentioned the Portfolio Management practice. It is of secondary importance for the alignment goal “Agility to turn business requirements Into operational solutions” in the cascade, but not less, than that. At the same time, it is of primary importance for the alignment goal “Realized benefits from I&T-enabled Investments and services portfolio” (ISACA, 2018, Objectives, pp. 298).

TOGAF states, that the EA Capability can be “chartered” to support portfolio and program management (The Open Group. 2022, Leader’s Guide). We assume, that this generally refers to the same projection of the (Agile) EA management on the processes

and roles, composing the portfolio management capability, ensuring the alignment of it with the company’s strategy.

And, again, for the PRINCE2 framework, Portfolio- as well as Program Management capability is regarded as a possible input, providing some of the standards for individual projects (PeopleCert, 2023, p. 8) (see Fig. 19).

Figure 19. Portfolio and Program Management in PRINCE2 (7) (source: PeopleCert, 2023, p. 8)

Fast forwarding to the Lean Startup framework, there is a concept of “Portfolio of [market] opportunities” to be mentioned here (Shepherd & Gruber, 2021, 971). This is to underline, that in the NPD domain, an important architectural task is to set a framework of dealing with ideas, even before they are converted into full-fledged BMs, as the task of converting an idea into a BM is already quite resource intensive.

The above discussed “Enterprise Architecture related capabilities”, relevant for the NPD-based BMI (see Table 1) are not to be seen as an exhaustive list. However, these are arguably the minimal scope to be considered in gap analysis, as follows from our literature research.

Capability	TOGAF® 10	COBIT 2019	SAFe® 6.0	ITIL® 4.0	PRINCE2® 7
Sensing business environment changes, requiring BMI	Business management capability	Managed Innovation (APO04)	Organizational Agility / Strategy agility, incl. Market sensing	Organizational Agility and organizational resilience, Strategy Management Practice	-
Making changes to the company’s	Enterprise Architecture Capability, ADM	Enterprise Architecture Management (APO03)	Enterprise Architecture Management across value streams	Architecture Management Practice	Consideration of the organizational context

architecture, enabling BMI			(Role: Enterprise Architect)		
Enabling creation, adjustment and integration of new BMs	Business architecture, BMI	Managed innovation (APO04)	Portfolio vision	Business and service architectures, Service Value System	Business case, Business layer
Creating and managing portfolios of BMI projects	EA Capability chartered to support portfolio	Managed portfolio (APO05)	Lean portfolio management	Portfolio management practice	The project context

Table 1. A non-exhaustive list of Enterprise Architecture related Capabilities, relevant for the NPD-based BMI

2.4.2 Product, service and project management related capabilities

What does the top-level capability of NPD have eventually to do with BMI? The often referenced “old” or “traditional” way is to first design an NPD-based BM, thoroughly plan the development of a product and then at some point deliver it with the hope of hitting the planned KPIs. That’s what SAFe for example calls preparing “overly detailed business cases based on speculative ROI” in the traditional approach as opposed to the lean-agile approach with “lean business cases with MVP, business outcome hypothesis, agile forecasting and estimating” to name a few differences (Scaled Agile Inc, 2023. Lean Portfolio Management).

What this practically means is that with the lean-agile or the Lean Startup approach, the BM is not fixed even during the NPD process. On the contrary, the NPD process in this case drives the BM development. Important to notice, though, that BM development in this case is the development of an “individual BM” as we saw defined by TOGAF before. The BMI, related to the “overarching BM”, e.g. to include the very possibility of adding NPD, starting from the strategy level and down to the realization, requires the previously discussed EA-related capabilities.

Established SMEs differ much from newborn startups. They have the backbone business with a track record and much more stakeholders to make happy. At least, at the start of the process. Acknowledging this difference, Viki et al. in their work “The Corporate Startup...” point at the necessity for the corporate executive to be given the opportunity of making informed decisions, when it comes to NPD. The Lean Startup

way here is to make sure, that only “validated BMs” are taken to scale, and that’s what management should be investing in (Viki, 2019).

The above is generally referred to as “validated learning” in the Lean Startup methodology. And this is exactly the NPD-based capability, that needs to be developed, if a company is following it. From the process perspective, this is called “The Build-Measure-Learn Loop” or cycle (see Fig. 20).

Figure 20. The Lean Startup Build-Measure-Learn Loop (source: Ries, 2017, p. 105)

We can derive the key capabilities from the methodology basics outlined by Ries in his more recent “The Startup Way...” book (Ries, 2017, pp. 85-86), making parallels with a more “established-business-related” framework, e.g. PRINCE2 7.

2.4.2.1 Determining the critical assumptions or success factors

The capability to determine and define critical assumptions of a BM idea – called “leap-of-faith assumptions” in the Lean Startup Methodology can be mapped to defining the “critical success factors (CSF)” in other frameworks. These are then used as inputs by the next capability to experimentally validate the product-based BM.

In PRINCE 2 this is generally mirrored primarily by the “Ensure continued business justification” principle and the “Business Case” practice (PeopleCert, 2023, pp. 20, 55). Although in this case, the assumptions regarding business justification – or achieving the desired outcomes and benefits for the stakeholders – are checked with the key stakeholders, including a “senior user” at the very start of the project, they are also not seen, as something immutable. At multiple checkpoints, generally at the end of each stage of a project, the project board is evaluating the results “so far”, checking if the

outcomes / benefits remain assured. And the business case evolves accordingly. That's the PRINCE2 version of the “build-measure-learn” loop: the “develop-check-maintain-confirm” project lifecycle with the addition of the “Learn from experience” principle (PeopleCert, 2023, pp. 21, 62).

2.4.2.2 Designing and building an MVP or a Prototype

Building a minimum viable product (MVP) – the most inexpensive (lean) version of a product, that allows to prove the critical assumptions experimentally – is arguably the core capability within the Lean Startup methodology. The MVP is tested against a group of selected users to either confirm the critical assumptions and scale or to pivot and possibly build another MVP as an iterative process – the “build-measure-learn” again. This helps achieve the necessary learnings at minimum cost.

Whereas PRINCE2 7 does not explicitly hint on iterations in the project’s progress, the principle “Manage by stages” provides for this approach through the “Plan-do-check-act” cycle within the Progress practice (PeopleCert, 2023, pp. 192-194) (see Fig. 21).

Figure 21. The PRINCE2 7 Plan-do-check-act cycle (source: PeopleCert, 2023, pp. 192)

In case of an NPD project, an MVP can be built within the next stage after the initiation stage. The product would be then checked by the project board, including the “senior user” as a part of the “stage boundary management” and if it becomes clear, that the expected benefits will not be achieved if the initial plan is followed, an according decision will be taken, and the business case and subsequently the BM updated.

While MVP is already a version of a product, however minimal it might be, there is a rather well-known methodology, used by Google Ventures under the name “Design Sprint”. The main point of this methodology is, that with a prototype, which is an even

less functional version of a product, which might even not be functional at all and is expected to be built within exactly five days, one can reliably prove the critical assumption about the future product, even without going for an MVP. The authors of the book on the methodology describe working with startup teams and being able to compress what would otherwise be months of work into a single week, avoiding “endless-debate cycle”. And instead of waiting to launch an MVP, they were getting clear data from a realistic prototype. (Knapp et al., 2016, p. 15).

2.4.2.3 Validated learning and pivoting

The ability to gather feedback and lessons learned from delivering a prototype or an MVP or its versions to the (potential) customers, based on the NPD-project iterations and stages, is part of both the Lean Startup and the PRINCE2 frameworks. The Lean Startup calls this “units of progress”, while PRINCE2 states the “Learn from experience” principle and requires maintaining a “Lessons learned log”.

The second part of this capability is to be able to dynamically adjust, or “pivot” the NPD-project. With the PRINCE2 “Manage by exception” principle this might be done even within a stage, if a deviation from the plan exceeds the tolerances.

2.4.2.4 Service Management

Neither the Lean Startup, nor PRINCE2 are specifically concerned with the post-NPD service management, in case the product is delivered to the customers in form of a service.

Eric Ries talks about the “sustainable growth” through feedback loops, measuring the traction with the customers (Ries, 2011). Ash Maurya calls this “The happy customer loop” (Maurya, 2022, p. 433). This can be regarded as a part of the service management capability, providing for the customer retention. However, there are many more aspects of it to be considered within the NPD-based BMI at an IT-Service company to make it sustainable.

PRINCE2 7 does not help here either, as the post-NPD service management falls under the “business-as-usual (BMU)” activity and capabilities, which are explicitly outside of the framework’s scope.

Hence, for IT-based business products, we would look for this capability into the IT service management (ITSM) frameworks, like ITIL 4.

We will not discuss this capability in detail here though, other, than seeing as a part of the BMI architectural gap analysis.

2.4.3 General (supporting) capabilities

The above discussed capabilities are by far not enough to secure sustainable BMI and capturing value from the introduced product-based BMs. They are the arguably most important new ones to be built. There are however other relevant capabilities, that are expected to be in place at established IT-Service SMEs but would need tailoring to be meaningfully applied to the new BMs.

These would include among others risk management, continual improvement of products, services and processes, information and especially knowledge management, relationship management and technology management.

Although the above discussed frameworks provide important guidance on each of these capabilities, defining them here is out of scope of this work. A comparative analysis could be the subject of a further research. Our approach here would be to empirically, based on expert interviews, determine the common patterns, that adjustments to these capabilities follow at the concerned group of SMEs to enable the NPD-based BMI.

3 Expert Interviews

3.1 The methodology and the approach

Following the Mayer's qualitative research methodology (Mayer, 2012) we focused on acquiring in-depth contextual first-hand knowledge from the purposeful sampled industry players and interviewees with a limited number of interviews, enough to achieve the data saturation. The latter was strictly limited to the common patterns and critical success factors in building the capabilities for the NPD-based BMI, as the whole spectrum of learnings and experiences on this path are colossal and diverse.

Our target group of interviewed companies:

1. German IT service and consulting SMEs with the background of custom software development and related services provided to the customers on the German market, including the major industrial companies, having developed and marketed own digital products apart from their main business or having such development currently in progress.
2. Business consulting companies and/or individual consultants, involved in the NPD-based BMI at the target group of SMEs.
3. Customers of the B2B products, developed and offered by the target group of SMEs.

Covering all these three groups of stakeholders helped us fully understand the context and the challenges of the discussed type of BMI, as well as assess the maturity of the developed capabilities. However, we aimed at achieving the data saturation specifically for the first group of interviewees, whereas the other two were considered as supplementary, confirming or highlighting the outcomes of the analysis of the first group's data.

In accordance with the chosen methodology, the prepared interview questions per group were of open-end type and served mostly as the door openers for individual in-depth discussions, as well as a roadmap helping not to miss the information, essential for the purpose of the current master thesis. Detailed questions varied, formulated dynamically context-based during the interviews. The questions also varied, depending on the personal role of the interviewee in the NPD-based BMI process at a given company.

Below are the blocks of the outline questions per company category, that were intended to be clarified in the talks with the interview partners. Although the eventual formulation as well as the number of questions varied, and further in-depth and contextual questions were asked, the interviews generally followed the outline and covered the planned scope.

The primary goal was to collect practical insights to contribute to the analysis, discussion and conclusions on the main research questions of the present master thesis. The secondary goal was to confirm, disapprove or correct the main contextual points derived from the literature research.

3.2 Questions to the SME management

1. What constituted your company's core business for the previous decade and who were the core customers? How would you characterize the dynamics of the market of your core business in the last five years – generally and from the perspective of your company?
2. What was the motivation and the trigger for starting an NPD-based BMI at your company? Do you consider your company organizationally agile in terms of sensing the market and adapting the strategy accordingly? How is this capability structured and how was it developed?
3. What were the considered alternatives to the NPD-based BMI and why have not they been implemented instead, or how successful is their implementation in parallel to the NPD?
4. Who was/is the trigger and/or driver of the NPD-based BMI at your company and how did the other stakeholders react to the change? How was the change enablement process structured? Which stakeholders and roles were the most affected by the change, how were they involved, how was the relevant communication structured?
5. If the NPD-based BMI was a major change to the company's BM, it required adjustments to some and development of new organizational and business capabilities, employee skills, processes and cultural changes. How was the gap analysis and the EA development in general performed?
6. How is the process of the development of new NPD-based BMs organized at your company? How was the capability built, what frameworks and

methodologies are/were used? What methodology is used for building the BMs and who is responsible for preparing and pre-evaluating them?

7. If you have or plan to have several new product-based BMs, or possibly several products for a BM, what is the process of selection, prioritization and budgeting of the product/BM ideas and projects? I.e. what is your company's approach to portfolio management for the NPD-based BMs? What did it take to build this capability, including management and employee skills?
8. How is the process of the NPD-based BM realization structured at your company? Is any established methodology (e.g. one of the lean-agile methodologies) used and why or why not? Are there e.g. project boards, product owners, business owners and other specific standardized bodies and roles?
9. What other, possibly already present capabilities were affected by the BMI, possibly needing development or adaptation? E.g. knowledge management, risk management, security management, etc. What was done to achieve this?
10. Do you consider the NPD-based BMI successful for your company, how do you measure success and what are the critical success factors and risks in this case? How would you characterize the maturity of the resp. business function at your company? What capabilities have deficits and/or are not mature enough from your perspective and how do you plan to improve them?

3.3 Questions to Business consulting companies and/or individual consultants

1. What advantages and risks do you see in the NPD-based BMI at the German IT Service SMEs
2. How mature do you consider the Organizational / Strategic agility and the EA management capability at this SME group? Are there structured processes and clear roles for the market sensing and triggering strategy adjustments? Are the strategy changes triggering a proper EA adjustment?
3. Where do you see the major deficits in terms of the NPD-based BMI related capabilities at this group of SMEs? Is the management of companies aware of these deficits? How are they dealt with?

4. What EA management and NPD frameworks do you use, when consulting these SMEs on the development of the relevant capabilities? What factors do you consider when tailoring them?
5. What are the main challenges for the NPD-based BMI at these SMEs, what are the critical success factors? How individual these challenges and factors are and what do they depend upon?

3.4 Questions to the Customers of the B2B products

1. What is your perspective on the dynamics of the IT-Services market in Germany, specifically for the SMEs offering custom software development services to the major market players?
2. What is your experience with the products (e.g. SaaS, PaaS, etc.), offered by the companies that you primarily work with as with IT-Service companies offering e.g. software development resources and custom software development? As compared to products offered by companies, built around own products initially. Are there important deficits in terms of capabilities?
3. Are there use cases where you would consider plausible substituting individually offered IT-Services with SaaS and PaaS from SMEs, thus potentially sharing costs and outputs with other market players?
4. What is your current policy and the strategy for the mid-term future for offering service contracts to German SMEs or substituting them with offshore and nearshore development (possibly through the SMEs) or insourcing and back sourcing?

3.5 The interviewees

Professionals representing 10 companies and the above 3 categories, involved in the German IT service and consulting industry, have been interviewed, based on the questions outlined above. We want to make it clear that as per Mayer's methodology the interviews were not expected to enable a quantitative analysis, which may be a subject of further scientific work and would need to involve a wider base of sources. However, the in-depth interviews covered a range of industry-characteristic setups and German geographical regions, providing a solid basis for qualitative analysis.

Most of the interviews were done remotely by phone or with the help of internet-based communication platforms. Two interviews were done as live meetings, in one case with two professionals representing one company. In another case one interviewee, being a private business consultant, was also engaged in projects at another interviewee's company, whereby they were interviewed separately representing different roles.

3.5.1 Categorization by business type

Most of the interviewed companies belong to the SME group, with four categorized by the number of employees as micro and small businesses (up to 49 employees) and three as mid-size companies (50-250 employees) (see Fig. 22).

Figure 22. Interviewed companies by category

3.5.2 Categorization by geography

Most of the interviewed companies are headquartered in Baden-Württemberg, South-West Germany. However, all the mid-sized IT-Services companies have branch offices in several German federal states, while both big clients are major international companies (see Fig. 23). All the interviewed company representatives are located at the company headquarters.

Figure 23. Interviewed companies by the federal state of the headquarters

3.5.3 Categorization by business role

Most of the interviewees were top managers of their companies, owning or co-owning them. Three of the interviewees have consulting as their major business role. The rest were either senior managers or combining product- and project management roles (see Fig. 24).

Figure 24. Interviewed professionals by business role

3.5.4 Demography

Although of no direct importance for the present master thesis, we decided to include the basic demographic statistics for the interviewed professionals, as it may or may not be useful for further scientific work.

Unfortunately, only one of the interviewees was female, which was by no means an intentional discrimination. And except for one of the interviewees, notoriously representing a big client company in a Product Owner / Project Manager role, the majority were native Germans to the best knowledge of the author, which, again was not a matter of intentional discrimination (see Fig. 25).

Figure 25. Interviewed professionals by business role

3.6 Discussion

In this section we will go together with the interviewees through the topics raised in the literature research as the main assumptions and context for answering the main questions of this master thesis. The latter will constitute the next section, i.e. the conclusions. We will also formulate possible fields of further related scientific work as the concluding accord.

3.6.1 The market pressure on the German IT-Service SMEs

The main contextual assumption of the present work was related to the market pressure, that the German IT-Service SMEs, specializing in the custom software development, experienced since the start of the COVID 2019 pandemic and through the economic “hard times” that followed. Based on the statistical data and academic research we assumed that this was a major factor prompting company management to strategically consider innovating the core BM with value streams, based on the NPD and marketing. But let us start with the discussion about the very phenomenon of market pressure on this group of companies.

Figure 26. If there was a significant rise in market pressure on the SMEs in the previous 3-5 years

Roughly 67% or two thirds (4) from the interviewed company representatives having commented on this matter, confirmed, that the market pressure on the German IT-Service SMEs in the field of custom software development was above the previous levels in the past few years. A third of the respondents (2) denied sensing any significant increase in market pressure relevant for their business segment (see Fig. 26). However, there were notable differences in categorizing the causes and the structure of the pressure.

3.6.1.1 Keeping away from the golf course

The increased market pressure on the SME segment was not mentioned as a significant factor by the respondents representing small companies, with most of their clients also belonging to the SME segment. For example, when asked whether the Corona period and the subsequent economic downturn had led to a reduction in projects, FS, owner and CEO of a small software development and consulting company in Hamburg, attributed the insensitivity to these factors precisely to the size of his company, which has 25 employees: "Maybe because we are not that big... we have development projects running in parallel all the time". According to the interviewee, a company of this size needs only about two new relatively long-running customer projects per year, and: "We have always managed to get these".

At the same time, when asked whether the trend or need to work from home during the pandemic had a positive effect on the number of projects due to the trend towards digitalization, the interviewee FS also denied this: "Nobody says 'thank God we had Corona, that's why we had good years'".

Interviewee SK, founder and senior manager of another small software development and consulting company based in Dresden, pointed to essentially the same company size factor, but on the customer side: "We are more rooted in the midmarket, so we are only indirectly affected by these big fluctuations, like today, when the automotive industry is [in stormy waters]. And that is something that does not bother me so much right now".

The company of SK has two long-standing corporate clients, but these are not critical to its revenue, so the company has "always been relatively insensitive to these general macro swings".

Remarkably, according to SK, staying in the middle segment is part of the company's strategy: "Because we are always very aware of the fact that at the end of the day, the question of whether you continue to have a contract depends on what is decided on

the golf course, so to speak. In other words, where you have no say at all. All the people you have to deal with can think you are great, but it does you no good because the decision is made five levels up. And of course, we always try to come to the point where we can take influence".

It is noteworthy that the medium-sized companies, whose core business is precisely individual software development and consulting in such "multistorey" corporations, talked about a substantial structural change in the process of winning new projects in this segment as an important sign of the times and business factor, relevant for the NPD-based BMI. The interviewee AW is a senior consultant at a medium-sized software development and consulting company, mainly in the SAP domain, headquartered in Stuttgart with branches in Hamburg and Bremerhaven. AW points out the dramatic changes that have taken place in recent years: "Things have changed a lot in consulting, too. In the past, you had a core customer, and it was always an ongoing process, where you said, "Okay, we are in with the customer, we have done a good project. And in the hallway, when you walked through the customer's rooms, you had the next project with you before you finished the other one. And that was such a seamless transition. And that is no longer the case. Today, there are more and more tenders, where you, as an existing supplier, have to think more and more about how you can get back into the game. On the one hand with existing customers, but also with new customers".

This is generally confirmed by interviewee JK, who is responsible for project and product management at the IT department of a large corporate customer in the Baden-Württemberg region: "Especially in terms of the budget, as it used to be... You just got a few resources and more on request. That was an e-mail. Those days are gone". He notes that this situation may be unique to this corporate customer and may be temporary, but it would not have happened without the economic downturn and its financial consequences.

Interviewee SS, co-owner and CEO of another midsize company headquartered in Stuttgart with several branches in southern Germany, points directly to the economic situation: "Market dynamics have two major aspects at the moment. One is the economic situation, where we see that customers, all of our customers, are basically having to cut back". However, he attributes more weight to another factor – the trend among corporate customers, for example in the automotive and retail sectors, to regard IT as part of their core business, which is reflected in the insourcing and back-sourcing

of development and innovation in order to be more flexible in this respect: "So that we are actually commissioned on a smaller scale or perhaps not at all. You can see that in the market".

This point is echoed in the input from the interview partner VKN, representing a major automotive market player headquartered in South Germany: "I sort of admit that there is a pressure, especially for German midsize IT companies, but I see a different reasoning for why it is so. So, from my perspective, it's not the point that the big companies are not having enough budgets or lack of projects. I see it in a different way. My reasoning is that the market is pretty dynamic. And it's so dynamic that every big company has to invest a lot in IT. What is driving IT from automotive side, is the major conversion or sort of transformation from the internal combustion engines to battery. And also there are other initiatives like digital transformation and also involvement of AI in the daily products. This is something that is basically pushing more of the budgets. There is a need of budgets to be pushed in because they have to keep up with the change to the market's demands. The software, like all the features of a tablet are expected by the customer. And they want to have quick over-the-air updates... The challenge where I see is, I would say, it's Europe's way of working and having less technical workforce. So, I see basically the competition is from the Asian companies. So yeah, partly I do agree that companies are trying to save costs as much as possible, especially on those activities which don't need too much innovation. And they are also trying to see how much can be brought in-house... So, to summarize, the challenge is coming with the cheap labor and the working hours also, this is what I see as challenging rather than on the budgets or on the project side".

This is confirmed by interviewee AW as a factor driven by corporate customers: "Yes, nearshore and offshore is a topic everywhere, no question. We are not yet active in this area, although we are in the process of validating this. Because some customers are explicitly demanding that, like, OK, you will only get a new framework contract if you offer at least this or that percentage of nearshore or offshoring. Then there is a cross price over the skill level table and in total it has to be so and so much cheaper". The interviewee SS from another medium-sized IT service provider puts more emphasis on nearshoring: "...Eastern Europe is putting more pressure on the market again, because there are also excess capacities there. Nearshoring. We do not want to talk about offshoring, but even there the competitive pressure is increasing, and we notice that there is already a price war when it comes to tenders. How it is conducted,

and how it ends up, is another question. That is also difficult, especially the environment. [The market pressure] is relatively high."

This is in line with what interviewee JK pointed out "from the customer side": "For me, nearshoring in particular is now the very big story in our context and offshoring hardly or not at all. But these IT hubs that we have somewhere, they play a big role, a successful role, an increasing role, I would say". These IT hubs are essentially the company's IT subsidiaries in Eastern and Southern European countries such as Bulgaria, Hungary and Spain, which combine the advantage of lower labor costs with relatively less different work and sometimes time zones cultures compared to offshore locations such as China, India, Southeast Asia or Africa.

Interviewee VKN supports the idea of having own IT hubs, especially for the infrastructure-related tasks, rather than outsourcing to external partners. He argues, that, on the one hand, "when we talk about the cloud infrastructure, it doesn't really matter whether it is located in Germany or whether it's located in some other country", but on the other hand, outsourcing Infrastructure, e.g. pipelines for the automated testing, causes delays in operations, if there is a rapid change requested. A matter of communication between different businesses. "That is costing them a little bit of time. So, to avoid this sort of delays, the company has set up their own internal sister companies so that they are always closely working with them for any new requirements and then to reduce the delivery time... Our own sister company is slightly on a low-cost place and then [we also] have more resources from there, from that company. Also given to sort of "best cost countries".

VKN also names the readiness of the personnel in the "best cost countries" to respond to calls virtually any time without a special SLA for that, as an important advantage, hinting on that the employees "might not have as great ... work-life balance in those countries... On the one side it is good that there is good work-life balance [in Germany], but this is in contrast to what is happening on the other side of the world." And when it comes to locations like South-East Asia or China, the time difference plays a positive role in the sense of work, requested at the end of the European business day, getting done over the European nighttime and ready by the European morning.

However, this pressure from other markets is seen by SS as an additional complication on top of the general need to cut budgets already mentioned and, what's remarkable, technological advances. SS argues that because of recent advances in process automation, aided by AI, many projects that would otherwise likely fall into the hands

of IT service partners have been put on hold or stopped altogether. "I think we are at the beginning of this, but we have to prepare for it. And I think the speed, the change and of course the technological progress has just increased tremendously. Decisions at the corporate level are being made a little bit faster or projects are simply being stopped or whatever. So, there is a lot of momentum. That is our situation, and we are at the end of the food chain".

JK also acknowledges this, pointing to the trend toward digitalization: "Perhaps especially in the last five years, there has been a major change that has pushed IT to the extreme and has now led to a situation in a company like ours in which extremely many processes that were unthinkable to handle electronically, especially in the area of procurement, could be digitalized overnight". On the other hand, JK points out that this trend and the above-mentioned factors in favor of more internalization of projects have led to another "aspect": "We may have a focus shift from full-service providers to "extended workbench." I think that will become a bit of a general theme."

What this "extended workbench" means in practice for an IT service company is explained in a comment by AW: "Often it is not always the project that is requested, but precisely a resource. And that makes it difficult, because in the past, people would say, okay, I will provide you with a team that will do it for you, no question. Today they say, well, he is a specialist in this field, and I want him and no one else, or else I will put it out there". And there is also a reference to another aspect of basically the same trend – that contracts are becoming shorter and shorter: "Also the project duration. We often have to re-acquire projects every six months, whereas in the past we used to have project durations of up to three years. And that has gotten a lot tighter".

All these structural changes in the German IT services market in the midmarket segment with large corporate customers are generally pushing down the profitability of traditional business relationships. "We are also in the classic sandwich position between employees, freelancers and customers - explains interviewee SS, - I think in the last, I don't know, two, three years, salaries have certainly increased by 10-15%, if not higher. And just for comparison, we have been able to raise prices for our customers by maybe 2-3%. That is also very little. In the last two years, they [the customers] were still relatively willing to talk. That is changing now, of course, because the demand is much lower, much more capacity is being offered on the market." That is, including nearshoring and offshoring, and relative to the number of projects being outsourced.

The last few years have been like that," AW says, "To say it straightforward, the salaries of IT professionals have exploded over the last 10 years. Can not say otherwise. Because simply ... the IT was always busy to get new capacities. As a result, the costs went up, or the salaries went up, and now we have the problem that the prices are going down for everybody, and that just does not go together anymore. Yes, inflation, all of that".

It is important to mention, that, while the interviewee VKN, representing the automotive industry, was talking about the vital necessity for the companies of this segment to invest more and more money in IT, this refers generally to the "OEM" part of the market. That is, where the "original equipment manufacturers" like the car manufacturers are integrating software, produced by 3rd parties, in their end products, e.g. embedded software, navigation, connectivity, entertainment, etc. At the same time, both SS and AW represent the IT-Service companies, not engaged in such "specialty products", but traditionally focusing on the corporate software, like SAP and other ERP systems, CRM, Data Warehousing, etc. Hence the differences in certain specific perspectives. To conclude this part, let's consider, that, while the small IT-Service companies that have already been successful on their market before, do not seem to be significantly affected by the recent market changes, the mid-size segment in the corporate software and consulting segment gets the pressure from the factors, listed in the Table 2.

No	Factor / Trend
1.	General shortening of IT budgets in this segment
2.	Advances in the field of process automation, including AI-assisted
3.	Insourcing, Backsourcing (internalization)
4.	Nearshoring
5.	Offshoring
6.	Extended workbench / contracting single resources
7.	Projects outsourcing via tendering
8.	Shorter contract times
9.	Sandwich situation: costs vs. tariffs

Table 2. Factors and trends, constituting the market pressure on the German mid-size IT-service (individual corporate software development and consulting) segment

3.6.2 What was the trigger for the NPD-based BMI

It is quite interesting how the sensitivity to the recent changes in the corporate IT-service market correlates with the causes that the interview partners named for the NPD-based BMI (see Fig. 27).

Figure 27. What was the trigger to start product-based BMI?

3.6.2.1 So much passion

Of the six companies for whom the question was directly relevant, only one cited an individual trigger that was not related to a specific business strategy. "Okay, no, that was different. In this case, it was our own product, a business analytics software, i.e. some kind of data analysis software, and that was actually such a pet project of mine, where I really put a lot, a lot, a lot of heart into it – explains interviewee SK, - I still think the idea is great, but it just turned out that it is really difficult to be perceived as a player in the market, and the product does not sell by itself". In other words, the company's first product was born out of an affinity of one of the founders and eventually failed on the market. But that was a trigger, and the second attempt was made with much more caution, although not actively sought: "There was a research project and people found each other and they built the whole thing, and it was financed by the city of Dresden and some other actors. And then they sort of split up and said: we don't want to do this anymore. And then they came to us and asked if we wanted to take over. And we had the advantage that it was already there, and we did not have this big initial investment. And what the app does technically is actually super simple, much, much, much easier than the other problem [The first product was much more complicated, which was one of the reasons for its failure].

3.6.2.2 Born out of necessity

Representatives from two midsize IT service and consulting companies cited recent market dynamics and the factors directly related to them as the impetus for starting work on their own products. At least on the business unit level.

For example, interviewee BS said that: "For the [business unit products], it really came out of necessity. We just had a rapid decline in the number of projects with the start of the pandemic. So, the economic situation. It was very difficult. And we were looking for interesting tasks for our employees, but which would also somehow bring something to the company that had an economic aspect. We had already developed a [product] within a customer project that created a connection between SAP and a big data platform. And then we just started to look at how we could standardize that. Then we stumbled upon the [widespread use case], and that is how we started to develop our own product with the goal of opening up the market. In other words, to get in touch with new customers via our product and to get further consulting projects this way".

The same situation of employees not being involved in customer projects due to market dynamics was cited by SS as a trigger: "This is one of the triggers, anyways. Technological development and the market situation. The two. That is a combination. ... And in the short term, of course, it is the market situation, that we also have free resources internally and then of course have to provide them with tasks. And of course, also to reduce the volatility or the dependence on individual customers".

3.6.2.3 Creating a more stable revenue base

Three more respondents pointed to the general strategy of achieving a more stable average income through balancing its sources to include product-based business lines. The latter included two small IT-service companies, who declared themselves not having been significantly affected by the recent general turbulence of the national economy.

In one of these three cases, the company's own product-based business and services were already a large part of the company's profits before the COVID-19 pandemic, but the strategy was still to stabilize income: "That was actually for different reasons. Depending on the situation, - MR explains, - we had products that actually came out of such a contract work. There were times when we said: okay, this would have been a commissioned work, or the customer came to us with a commissioned work, and then we said, yes, we want to do this as a product so that it remains our property, and we charge a license fee. Another reason was to create a more stable income base...

But it is enough if we make at least a third [part of the total revenue].... With the contract work we always had the problem that we either had a lot to do and little time to take care of new orders. Or we had little to do and then, and frankly you do not get new orders overnight". MR also points out that the first product idea came from a customer. However, the decision to offer it as a product rather than a service was made by his company.

Exactly the same pattern was given by interviewee FS, who owns and manages a small IT services company in Hamburg: "These were our customers. A customer was looking for a solution to her problem. We implemented it for them, and then they came up with the idea that if we liked it so much, others might like it too. And then they simply asked us if we would like to do that, and so we did, and now we have our own product. It is a partnership. We have a minority stake. Yes, but it was an opportunity for me".

In principle, this means that the customer provides a significant portion of the financing as well as market expertise: "It is the case that the customer bears the innovation risk, which we cannot estimate. What are the chances that the business will be really successful? That is why we do it this way. We never go at our own risk". But we will come back to that later.

A colleague of FS, interviewee TN, who also works as an independent consultant, sees the need for stability and scaling as the main trigger here, rather than the issue of "free resources", although there is of course an interdependence: "I wouldn't even say increasing utilization [is the main motivation]. That's also a need, but you want to decouple a little bit, you want to bring in stability, you want to maybe have the control yourself and not always be dependent on the customer... These are some of the things that drive you to build your own product, to bring in scalability and stability. So that even if the customer cancels, you still have a regular income".

TN also explains what he means by "scalability" in this context: "Because scaling means, yeah, okay, there comes another project, but I have to hire two new devs at the same time. That means you always scale linearly, not exponentially, because a new acquired commissioned project means you always have to hire new people. It also means, of course, you make a little profit per dev. And the more devs you have, the more profit you have. But you can never really scale. And if a customer cancels and you don't get a new project right away, then you have five people sitting around who don't make anything. So that is always a slippery slope." However, TN also warns that this scalability can't be achieved just by redirecting existing resources to product

development; product management and sales also play an important role and can't be done as a "side hustle".

Exactly this "scaling", together with a more stable income structure, is mentioned by the interviewee DFB, which represents a medium-sized market player with more than 25 years of company history and a range of its own marketed products: "For about two years, we have been pursuing the goal of looking more systematically for ideas that can be developed into successful products. One reason for this is to diversify our revenue structure and thus become more resilient to market fluctuations. Another is to be able to scale revenues through mechanisms such as licenses or subscription models, rather than through the number of people employed".

Here, DFB does not directly say that this new approach was triggered by recent events in the market. However, we could assume that it was a combination of that and the level of product development and management methodology and practice achieved in his company. As for the start of the process, DFB reveals a slightly different path from customer projects to own products: "In fact, the first products came from solutions that we used in individual customer projects and that were improved over time through use in various projects. If such a solution has reached a very good degree of maturity, the further development to a product is a manageable step with a manageable effort. This is how we developed our first products".

3.6.3 Capabilities: sensing market changes, enterprise and organizational agility, enabling BMI

3.6.3.1 Size matters

The mere fact that all the interviewed IT-Service companies at some point adopted a BMI in form of own-product-based business is evidence of their enterprise agility, i.e. they could surpass the initial boundaries of their core business, although only in a small percentage of cases the new business models presently account for a significant part of the revenue.

The organizational agility concept is a bit more complicated, when applied to the companies of this segment. Basically, it presumes that a company is able to restructure its processes or build new ones in response to the new market-driven strategies – in our case, that'd be the processes, necessary to ensure the acquisition of NPD-based BMs, their evaluation and implementation to the level of new stable value streams.

This breaks down into several capabilities that we are discussing on the next pages. Here we start with the capability of market sensing in regard to NPD-based BMs. And in this respect, what follows from the limited number of interviews we made, is that size matters. Only two of the six relevant interviewed companies have developed or are developing specific processes and establishing organizational structures for market sensing and collection of BM-ideas. Both belong to the upper part of the mid-size segment, whereas in smaller IT-Service companies there are no organizational structures, specifically responsible for this process and it appears completely “opportunity driven” (see Fig. 28).

Figure 28. Organizational structures for the identification of candidate product-based BMs

In the case of a medium-sized IT service and consulting company in Cologne, represented by DFB, the responsible structure is the long-established Research and Development (R&D) department: "In this sense, research and development has two main tasks. On the one hand, it is about evaluating new methods, technologies and tools and building up the corresponding skills and competencies that we use or could use in our customer projects. ... On the other hand, it is about observing and analyzing the technology market. We assess, which topics, technologies and tools will be relevant in the future, as this is important for future-proof investments, for example. If we recognize a systematic need for a technology or a tool in our projects, which cannot be covered by the available tools, we have the possibility to go in this direction with our own developments and possibly develop a product or a consulting service. This has resulted in products that we now market in addition to our core services, or better said, that we offer together with or as part of our core services".

The interviewee SS, representing a medium-sized company in Baden-Wuerttemberg, identifies three channels for the new product-based BMs: "The first is that we recognize a need in the market from our business practice and evaluate it. Second, we use our

network to find partners who bring ideas to us and ask for a partnership. Or "c", there are employees who have an idea and maybe have already done some tests, which they would like to bring in, because they do not have the resources to implement it on their own". And exactly for the third channel there is an established "coordinating body or mechanism", which we can think of as a pipeline for the new BM ideas generated by employees. Formally, this can be seen as an elementary organizational structure for market sensing, although SS did not elaborate on that.

3.6.3.2 Gut feeling

For the rest of the group of companies interviewed, Senior Consultant AW, representing a smaller but still medium-sized IT company from Stuttgart, summed up the essence very precisely: "Gut feeling. We have a colleague who has a pretty good intuition when it comes to new technologies and what the market is looking for, and he assumed that it would go down well, and he did the first development work, and I think that was the result. We did not expect it at all". And there was a negative answer to the question whether they had institutionalized this capability.

In other cases, it comes from the project business, as described by interviewee SS above. "Actively searching for [ideas, new BMs] is not something for us, because we are quite small - explains MR, CEO of the smallest company in the group - so, as I said, [product ideas emerge] through requirements that come to us, where we then say, okay, there could be a market behind it. Or through ourselves, that we ourselves have thought that there could be a market. We actually have no process, nothing like that".

3.6.3.3 Close contact

The interviewee OD manages another small software company in Kiel, which has developed in the opposite direction during its 25-year history. The company was initially product-based, but over the years added product-related and product-independent individual software development as a service as BMs. And although in-house product development is still the backbone of the business, there is no dedicated market-sensing organizational structure that would look for NPD-based BMs: "That's where you really have to do a market analysis. You have to go there and say: Who are the target groups? How can I address them? How does it have to be tailored? What can a pricing model look like? ... What does the customer need? Who am I addressing? That is not possible. ... No, no, we are too small for that with 20 employees. Microsoft,

big companies: there are dedicated product managers and dedicated marketing people who together think about what the market could need, and that is more or less well-founded, that is more or less based on scientific methods. Yes, if you are product-oriented, then of course you have to do product management. Then of course you always have to keep your eyes and ears open to the market and think, what are the customers asking me here? That is the beauty of service contracts. Not only do you earn money, but you are always close to the customer. If you notice that the markets are changing, that the customers are changing because of economic and social changes, then very quickly there are demands on the product world. And if you are very close to the customer, then you can react very quickly. If, for example, you would only sell your products via platforms and you actually have no direct customer contact yourself, then I would say that it will be difficult for you as a company".

The importance of having a close contact with the client in this context is also confirmed "from the client" side by VKN: "They [a major product company on the automotive market] have very strong SaaS or PaaS or licensing models. They started with just giving the resources to the automotive field. Then slowly they try to understand what is the requirement, and then based on that they try to create a minimum viable product, an MVP, instead of a service. So, they say okay because that is also something which the OEMs will say: yeah, it's fine, because the OEMs will not invest completely on that. Because when we say that this product could be reused by other, other companies, other OEMs, then it's like a win-win. IT companies will say: okay fine, I will fund say 40% of the product by my side and you take up 60%, because the first product is basically serving you. And then that product would be made maybe slightly customized for others or perhaps it could be used as such. But that would be one thing I noticed where we need a, you know, very good understanding of what the customers are looking for because customer will not go for each and every problem to each and every company there".

3.6.3.4 No frameworks

Given the answers above, you would not expect this group of companies to use an EAM framework to structure the relevant business processes. Not even in the upper segment. Even the "most structurally advanced" participant from Cologne talked about in-house designed EAM processes, although some elements of them may come from the tailoring of EAM frameworks: "No, we are not currently using a formal enterprise architecture model. We have our proven company/project structures, processes and

values, and everything we do is based on these elements. These enterprise elements are extensively documented in Confluence. We may follow the principles of such frameworks/procedures (classical or often agile) while adapting them to our specific needs. One could speak of a best-of-breed approach”.

3.6.4 Capabilities: designing new BMs

We are talking here specifically about the capability and process of thinking through and formalizing a BM behind each new own product, before it goes into implementation. This is a rather expensive risk management tool, requiring certain skills, knowledge and resources. No surprise, that this was not to be found at the minor SMEs from the interviewed group, except for a company specializing in product management consulting. Small IT-Service companies take a different, more generic and in a way a less risky approach (see Fig. 29).

Figure 29. Use of formalized business models at the start

3.6.4.1 Okay, you got your money

The most systematic, methodical and experience-based approach we see, where the relatively large size of the company meets a multi-year track record of product-based value streams. Interviewee DFB talks about two different types of product-based BMs that his company designs and manages: "This is one way to build a BM. You combine service components with license components. It is also possible that a product is financed only by licenses... What the right BM is, must be planned during the development of the product and tested in the market. It is also possible that the BM changes during the development process and the revenue share shifts from services to licenses. This is why we work with Lean Canvas, and ideally with the Lean Startup

method in general, so that we can pursue the most promising ideas. And when it comes to planning, we have built up an understanding of the market over the years through our own experience and know-how. We have a good feel for what a product cycle or curve should look like for a successful SaaS product. Based on that, we can plan and control relatively well”.

The company, represented by SS, is of the same size in terms of number of employees as the previous respondent but has only entered the product-based business domain in the last few years. It is formalizing product BMs, but also admits that it has a long way to go in terms of sales forecasting: "At the end of the day, I think we need a relatively uniform template where we get past the points that are relevant. And above all, we need a sparring partner who will challenge everything that comes in. And then we have to build up experiences step by step to cover the realities... I think all this is also quite well verifiable via a matrix or a form, I'd say. Maybe you need some experience with calculations, and so on. But I think our people can already calculate development costs or something like that quite well. But what we all still have to learn is how to work with sales and how close to reality we are with our ideas, what the effects or the interaction between marketing, sales and the actual order is. And that, I think, is where we have the biggest gaps”.

In any case, this is seen as a risk management measure in the sense of protecting the investments that in this case are generally made by the company itself. And the consultant TN describes the BM formalization with the Lean Canvas as an investor management procedure: "So a Business Model Canvas or something like that is usually at the very beginning to convince investors that you need money, that they will give you money. Like that. And then at some point it is like: yeah, okay, you have convinced us and this is very promising, you get money for it”.

However, it is important to note that the Lean Canvas is a formalization of BM, but not in the sense of a detailed business plan. Calculations can and should be done in the background, but details are not expected.

3.6.4.2 Let's start developing and see what comes out of it

The interviewed company from the midmarket segment did not initially consider the business results of its own product development as a significant driver, hence no business modeling: "At the beginning, our focus was precisely on capacity utilization, on having interesting tasks" - explains BS. The business component was then secured through a key partnership, so in principle the major business risks were simply avoided:

"We got in touch with our current partner company very quickly. And that has definitely opened up further doors for us because of their market status - [our partner] is the market leader in the area of [...] – and opened further doors for us. But there was definitely no real business plan behind it. The application cases, what kind of business case is behind it, is not important to us. We are completely focused on the technical interface. And that sometimes makes it difficult in sales to show something when there is nothing there [laughs]".

However successful the first shot may have been, the need for at least some form of investment risk management becomes apparent as more products and product features come online. The co-interviewed Senior Consultant AW from the same company refers to this as a form of controlling: "...we used to just say we are going to develop and see what comes out. Now we have also started internally to do some kind of controlling on the new topics. That we say, we just put a volume behind the new topics, a business development budget, that we can say, okay, now we are allowed to invest 200 days in this topic and then we put our cards on the table, how does it really look like, have we gained anything from it or is it even sustainable from the costs and everything. Because that has been very difficult for us now that we have taken on topics. A lot of people have been working on it, and a lot of capacity has gone into it, and we are now going to approach such new developments in a more structured way in the future".

Although it might be a part of controlling (see Fig. 30), the approach, described by AW, is rather what is defined as "Appetite" in the "Shape Up" project management methodology for product development at Basecamp: "We call this the appetite. You can think of the appetite as a time budget for a standard team size" (Singer, n.d.). Although Shape Up operates in smaller cycles – up to 6 weeks for a team of up to 3 people, making it some 90 working days – the principle is the same.

Figure 30. Mission- and KPI-based Controlling (Gadatsch & Mayer, 2013, p. 55), unofficial translation

3.6.4.3 The invoice is on its way

The Shape Up methodology was also explicitly mentioned by SK from a smaller IT company from Dresden: "I've seen this very often with other companies that I know very well. That they had a product and at some point they didn't calculate it economically or they didn't keep an eye on the costs in the sense of "my people got nothing to do anyway". And we try calculating everything we do through the number of hours and the hourly rates. I would not say that we succeed in doing that with all the things that we do internally, but we are getting better at that. And I think the product companies benefit from this way of thinking. And we have also tried out a lot in terms of methodology and learned a lot from Basecamp [Shape Up], for example".

However, companies in the smaller size segment of the surveyed group prefer not to pay for their own "appetite satisfaction". As SK explains: "We said from the beginning that we would take over the [product] and continue with it, because it costs us little, but we would get paid for the further development... and [we] are now so far that we get a large part of the further development financed by small projects. ... That was just a different mindset. That is a difference to, yeah, we must first invest heavily ourselves before we even come to the point that we can show that to somebody. And now it is rather the case that we say, yes, we also have ideas for this, and we would also like to

push this further, but we are doing it at the pace that the market dictates. Up to a certain point".

A similar but even more "customer-driven" approach to product funding, where the first customer pays for development and becomes a partner, is demonstrated by OD, who runs a product-first IT company: "[Business modeling] doesn't really play that big a role. We have a standard approach, customers come to us, and we see that there is a need and the customer is interested in working with us. The first step is that we do a workshop with all the stakeholders who can contribute in some way, and then we work out the current state and the target state together. Where do we want to go? What do we want to do? And there is already a charge for this service. The results belong first of all to the client, and in the ideal case they come out of such a workshop. So, in the first step a partnership and a cooperation are created".

In this sense, the smallest interviewed company is an exception and comes closer to the medium-sized segment in terms of investments and has similar experience-based concerns regarding the "free" resources: "...The investments were, let me just say, 90% time – explains interviewee MR, - Actually, that was a problem for a long time, that we practically did not realize that time is also money". Here, however, with more than 10 years of product business history, there is an even more critical evaluation of not having used BM as a tool: "We also had to adjust prices and so on. More in retrospect. But that was actually the last 10 years, we have neglected that a little bit. But that was our mistake, that in the last 10 years nothing was actually calculated. Something was just developed and offered, and some price was asked for it. But nobody thought about how much you can charge or something like that".

But according to MR, the "mistake" was compensated by... well, you already know by what, right? "...It is smarter to do this [business modeling] first. That is clear. But it is also only a success factor, so to say, but no precondition. So, if you do not do this, it is not automatically, that you have no success. But if you do it, of course, the probability of success is higher. We were lucky that we were halfway successful in those areas, maybe because you can deduce... because we were not that bad in the evaluation. So, maybe our *gut feeling* was not so bad".

3.6.5 Capabilities: portfolio management

As it follows from the interviews in this segment, portfolio management in terms of selecting best NPD-projects out of a structured pool for the investment and implementation, is generally not a methodologically addressed area within the group. For the companies with a track record in product development, this is again either a matter of "gut feeling", as MR puts it, or a customer-focused approach to adding new features to an existing product, as explained by BS: "We do not customize our software, we bring everything into the standard software... If there is really a strong customer request [to have a unique feature]... Then we also go to the customers in these cases and find agreements with them that they bear part of the costs". Here, BS is talking about features, but given the specifics of the company's product portfolio, this would also include new SAP-related products.

The same goes for a smaller IT consultant in Hamburg (FS): "Then you really have to try to evaluate it with some canvas to see where you start. But we are not there yet. We just have this one option where we develop the product with the partner".

And as if in response, SS from a larger SME states: "...In principle we must of course first make a certain evaluation of each idea. It should be more or less the same [template] so that we can compare them. One thing is also clear, we cannot follow up on thirty ideas, we simply do not have the capacity". But this is not yet about managing a portfolio of generally accepted product ideas and choosing which ones to implement first. This is really about having a finer filter for accepting such ideas in the first place, although basically the same evaluation would be used to manage a portfolio if it already existed.

TN sums up the situation well: "I can tell you that most of the companies I have worked with have been overwhelmed by one idea. Even in our area it is very rare that they try several ideas at the same time. Basically, of course... it can always be like that. You have several ideas and you want to see which ones we should focus on. And there one must consider, okay, how can we measure that anyway? Who says that one idea is better than the other? Well, big companies for sure. They might build several MVPs and see which one works best in the market. But I think this is really only for big professional companies".

3.6.6 Capabilities: Product, service and project management

3.6.6.1 Product ownership: it's not that easy

There was a tapestry of experiences and opinions regarding the product ownership capability in IT service companies starting or continuing product-based business. On the one hand, at least the theoretical part seems to be quite clear from the experience of working on customer projects: "Since we [originally] did not develop our own products, we did not play this role ourselves, but told our customer how to do it and therefore knew everything - explains FS, - but we can [now] better understand the problems and challenges product owners have, because we now have our own product and see that this is not so easy. The whole stakeholder management, to make straightforward decisions... And so we are learning a lot about it ourselves, because theory is one thing and practice is the other".

Others, like SK, get not only the theoretical part, but also the practical experience in product management from the customer projects: "We also have the good fortune to work with our customers on a very long-term basis... Even if [our company name] is not written on it, it is in fact a web application for which we are also responsible for its productive operation and maintenance, and which is continuously developed for or with our customers. In this respect, it is often the case with customer projects that we have product responsibility over a longer period of time".

That's practically a kind of outsourcing of product ownership, although there were also doubts expressed as to whether that was even possible: "That stays with the company, yes. A software provider can never be so deep in your domain that he can take over the product ownership – argues TN, - but of course it has to be established in the company that there is a product owner. That always sounds so easy, but that has to be established in the company so that they can make decisions. And that is often not the case".

SS, who represents a larger SME but whose product business is still in its infancy, more or less agrees with both opinions: "I also believe that we currently have the skills in individual aspects. But of course, we have never been responsible for an entire product and its entire life cycle. And that is something new. Definitely". At the same time, SS raises an interesting aspect of what is usually understood by "entrepreneurship" as a skill that can be developed and trained to a certain extent but is also second nature: "The capability of a product owner, let me say, to put ideas on paper and so on, you can learn that. Maybe, okay. The capability of intrinsic motivation

and the drive to follow new ideas and to expand the product through commitment and interest, curiosity, etc... I think we have to recognize which people have this potential or maybe even have to recruit them from the market”.

This is a very important conceptual part, because the terminology can be a bit tricky. So, when BS talks about an established product ownership within her software development team, she is referring to the Scrum definition of the product owner role for an agile team: "In the development team we have that already. There is a clear project management, there is a product owner for each [product], there are already structures that we have established quite well. This is a key role in the Scrum methodology, responsible for the product backlog, etc., but should not be confused with the broader, business-related concept of product ownership with an entrepreneurial character.

She then goes on to explain that another team is responsible for the customer and service management aspect of product management: "We are in the process of separating our development team a little bit from a service team, which then handles customer requests, both initial requests from new customers as well as customer support for existing customers. We now do that through a ticket system, so that we can take care of maintenance requests. Also technical support requests. And the team is still a little bit under construction. We are in the process of establishing a project management system”. And that brings us to the next two capabilities.

3.6.6.2 Service management: a luxury problem

Since service management in the sense of IT service management (ITSM) is limited to a given product or application management, there is no need for a statistical chart here. Only one respondent – unsurprisingly from the top SME segment with several products and many years of experience in this business – stated that it structures its service management with formalized methodologies and top-level tools, although apparently not to the extent of a full-scale ITSM framework like ITIL: "For one of our most successful products with a large number of customers, we are using a DevOps approach and Jira Service Management as a tool. The latter is an ITSM tool that defines the processes externally. How the tickets are resolved internally in the team is again our individual process. We see this as the most important success factor for the entire product business. You have to have a very good understanding of the customer's needs and be in constant contact with the customer in order to iteratively develop solutions”.

The key words here are probably "the large number of customers" and "the constant contact with the customer". Although there is no overall quantitative definition of the first, none of the other companies interviewed seems to be at this stage, which is then considered a good enough reason not to implement a full-fledged ITSM yet. For example, SS, the CEO of the second of the midsize companies surveyed, sees the development of the service management capability as a future task: "Of course, it is also a new capability. But we are a little bit less worried about it, because we do not have any products that suddenly bring 1000 customers or something like that. We can certainly grow gradually with the requirements. Of course, we have to make the right architectural and conceptual decisions, but that is not a giant leap, it is a growing process, if you will, or an increasing learning curve that can be accompanied. I wouldn't worry too much about that either".

However, similar to product management in general, the relevant experience comes from customer projects (for corporate customers): "Exactly, there we orientate ourselves at the classical ITIL processes or similar, i.e. in the direction of ITSM, corresponding service management processes. The metrics are also known to us. They are also established with the customers, and that is the way we learn or apply them if needed". - explains SS.

AW, representing the middle segment of SMEs, told us the same thing, but in a more "poetic" style: "We've been doing application management for a customer for about 20 years, and so we know the ITIL processes... And so, they already diffused into our blood, and we're actually applying them one-to-one. Without saying that we are working according to the ITIL standard. We already have that in the blood, so it definitely goes in that direction".

With varying concentration of ITIL in their blood, smaller companies generally prioritize a closer, less formalized connection to the customer. "Well, I think I did some ITIL training, that was helpful to understand a bit how it works, - agrees SK, - but we do not have a classic framework because we are very value-driven. That sounds very trivial, but something like values, healthy human understanding, quality as a value... that I am still trying to explain, what does that actually mean? What does that mean in practice? Actually, we want people to be able to make good decisions for the customer and for us. And that is actually our answer rather than a strict framework with an SLA, to put it bluntly".

Well, as I said, we don't really have processes like that, - says MR on the subject of ITSM, - You can send us an e-mail. We also have a support portal, you can write an e-mail, you can call and then the employee will take care of it. This is usually the same person who developed the program. And they do support directly and that is enough for now. So, it is not so many requests". So, unlike the larger company, where service is structurally separated from development, here we see that in a smaller organization the merging of these activities is the norm. Maybe even seen as an advantage.

In fact, both representatives of the corporate clients eventually do see this close contact as the decisive advantage in terms of service management. This comes from the interviewee from the automotive industry: "...so, in one case they are not setting up a real nice customer portal where we say we raise a ticket and then tickets get solved. They say: this is a person, anything you have, just reach him. So, he will make sure that your issues are resolved. So, he will bring up his technical teams, he will bring up everything, he will come on site, he will fix it. So, sometimes it is still fine. You can survive without a real big infrastructure for customer support. If you could have some dedicated people there at least as a key account holder, key customer manager, something like that, which is still manageable until you... go up to, you know, thousands of people... like some 5 – 6 thousand people coming, then it is a different thing. But here we are having few leads who always say okay, they can always contact this person. So, it's still fine, it's still manageable for the initial stages, I would say MVP or even companies like [a big SaaS player on the OEM market], they are also giving, you know, they are huge, they get huge money, but they are keeping one dedicated person for each project. Of course, sometimes they charge for that, but still they say he's available all the time and he will be there, here."

And exactly losing this kind of direct contact is seen by the other corporate representative as the major risk factor, when switching the relationship from custom software development to something like a SaaS.

A good summary on the one hand, and another hint from a technical perspective comes from TN: "...these are luxury problems [service management]. I mean, at the beginning I do not have to worry about: oh my god, how are we going to support the thousands of users later on? These are luxury problems. The first step is to see if the product works at all. And in development, we always say that whatever we build, even an MVP, has to be maintainable and extensible. On this basis we start to build. Simple, high-quality, extensible and usable... [And] if you now notice that your MVP is so

successful, it goes through the roof. Well, you have to think about that. Now we need people to support it”.

3.6.6.3 Management by Exception

Nowadays one can hardly find a software development team, that would not declare itself working according to some agile project management methodology – Scrum, Kanban, XP or a mixture, or some customized version thereof. In practice, this may be quite far from the reality, but that’s not a subject of our research. An interesting observation from the bulk of the interviews is that the word “controlling” was mentioned hardly less often, than “agile” in the context of project management. In the vast majority of the cases, at least on the start, the role of project manager is merged with the role of product owner and manager, who generally “drives” the whole story on her own. However, proportionally with the size of the company, number of products, their maturity and the track record, the importance of controlling grows.

"Project management, yes. In the beginning, we really did cut back on that. But we were only three at the beginning," explains BS.

"Do we need a project manager every time? I think I would be cautious, because that would automatically increase the overhead, - says SS, - and I think it is one of our advantages that we are lean, small and agile and can make decisions on short ways. But we still need a kind of clamp, yes, I think, which coordinates and summarizes everything a little bit, so that everything goes in the right direction, and you also get time windows in which you have to do exactly that, so that a certain reporting happens... And then we also have to look at how we can still track and follow the whole idea objectively... I want to have 10 new customers in the next quarter. If I only get two, I have a huge problem. Then my business case no longer fits. I also have to figure out how to get these 10. Do I have to make 100 calls a day, 50 calls a day? And I have to keep track of all that, because otherwise I will not be successful”.

And again, not surprisingly for the "heavyweight" product developers from Cologne, it is as good as you would expect from a big company: "We have a general controlling system in which the products are embedded as soon as they generate sales. On the quantitative side, we have annual plans that are compared with actual figures on a monthly basis. On the qualitative side, we plan which measures are to be implemented in the coming year. In addition to the sales figures, we track KPIs that deal with various aspects of the product (especially traction). The typical product development is done with agile methods, typically Scrum or a similar approach in combination with methods

from innovation management and product management. But when it comes to individual product-related decisions, we trust the product owner". Management by exception (PRINCE2)? "- Yes, something like that".

3.6.7 Capabilities: Prototyping, MVPing, Validated learning

Over the previous decades the concept of minimal viable product (MVP) got so implanted into the software engineering community, that this is arguably the first thing one would think of in terms of idea implementation. Sometimes a different naming was used, but the general idea of first developing a very limited version of a product with the most important, or indispensable features only and using it for the calibration of the product, based on the feedback from the users, was more or less directly communicated in every interview.

In MR's terminology, the MVP concept is called "pre-product: "We just put the pre-product out to the people and then improved the product based on the feedback. This would be practically the same as if you made the prototype, gave people testimonials or something, and improved the product based on that".

The prototype referred to here is an artifact of the Design Sprint methodology, an even less functional version than the MVP, but generally serving the same purpose, which is to confirm that the critical assumptions about the future product are correct. Interviewee SS calls them "KO criteria", although they also include technical feasibility and a proof of concept (POC) to test it, which is not part of Design Sprint prototyping, for example: "...the first thing would be to define the technical feasibility. So, to do a POC... and to say, yes, that works. Yes, technically it is often a smaller hurdle... Otherwise I do not need to go to the market. And then we certainly need to have a first stripped-down MVP approach where we can also test the technicality and then say, okay, can the customer really make something of it, and would it be usable in reality? And then it is not so much about the technology, but whether the business functionality and the market needs are covered. And for that we need a concept, of course, a procedure model, which we also have, or have defined, and then of course we have to stick to that. I just wanted to say that it is very, very important that we do that. For sure. Where we then say, okay, we can exclude these KO criteria and then the big investment starts. Before we start this big investment, we should have these technical and business aspects resolved".

Consultant TN warns, however, that the prototyping concept of the Design Sprint can be misused if it is validated against investors and not against users: "You need different methods to do that. And then in the next step it is also about the fact that you first build some kind of click dummies or something like that, prototypes, in order to get closer and closer to something tangible from this rough idea. And there are different ways to do that. You can do a Design Sprint where you iterate a little bit... the result might be that you have a prototype that you use. But sometimes we also experience that these things have already happened in advance and then the investors, after they have seen these prototypes and so on, have said, "Okay, we can put money in there".

And this can lead to "overbuilding" the MVP because the funding was already secured: "But I tell you, - TN continues, - what usually happens is that this business canvas, prototype, everything is done, and then the companies are so convinced of their hypothesis that they now think this is it. So. And then they start to develop and then they have really good software developers, well, then they build, build, build to the MVP. The problem is often that this MVP is much too big. That means, they build, they put two years into development, then they have this MVP, which is already much too expensive".

And actually, we have confirmation from the "big business" side (VKN), that one doesn't necessarily need an MVP first, but essential is to get feedback from the customers, cooperate with them: "you can come up with something which you are good at. So, some sort of ideas, you can say, okay, we will show this one. Okay. And then you can suggest basically... Sometimes it could be just sort of ideas as well, or some sort of a prototype. And then, and invite most relevant people from your customer, from your customers, especially teams, and then slowly scale it to other relevant customers. And then you can also say, if you have ideas which you would think will help, you can also come up with some sort of proposals. So, it's like also basically a day of, yeah, brainstorming."

In this context, the situation is different, or rather individual, when a product is developed in close contact with a specific customer or business partner. In such a case, MR rejects the idea of non-functional prototyping altogether: "Rather directly a functional one. Okay, well, in the software domain you can't do that in a prototype... Well, maybe internally, but when you come in front of the customer... [then no]".

The other case described by AW is when the prototyping is already done directly with the customer: "This prototyping is actually already being done with the customer. That

was a customer project. That is exactly where we go with a new product. We developed it together with the customer. They have said we cannot bear the full development costs, you may then continue to roll out this product, that is all right, but we have not yet had a purely internal project where we have done prototyping and everything else". BS, the interviewed colleague of AW, who is directly responsible for a number of SAP-related products, points out the difficulty of using prototypes to collect feedback when a product is "purely technical" in nature: "If I go back to the [products], the question is what prototyping is... we don't have a user interface, it's a purely technical tool, I can't build a click dummy and show it like this. But we had a fully functional product with which we then went to our partner. They have an app store for this kind of [products] and said: here, we can open it for you, and what we needed to do to make it happen. And that was kind of our go-to-market, that we established ourselves in their app store and then the first requests came to us".

The authors of the Design Sprint methodology argue that "you can prototype anything", if you adopt "the prototype mindset" (Knapp et al., 2016, p. 168). However, given the specific circumstances for the product and the goals, the question is rather, if that would be exactly the lean way.

And again, having a prototype is no guarantee of success. Here's an important quote from SK about one of their failed products: "Well, it was done more or less lean-agile. We had a team that worked on topics in sprints. That was not the problem. The problem was, I think, that we had a prototype, but when it came to assessing whether the market really needed it, we probably lied a little to ourselves, to put it bluntly. In the sense that people tend not to tell you in the face what an [inappropriate] idea it is. That is also difficult, of course, and I think we probably did it along the lines of: Yeah, look how easy and great this is. And then really just lost the focus".

The Design Sprint methodology pays a lot of attention to customer interviews as part of prototyping, but this requires experience, of course. In software engineering, this is also to some extent part of the agile approach. According to TN, the two can be combined perfectly: "What is so commonly mentioned is the Scrum framework, which is exactly designed for you to collect feedback iteratively and quickly. That means you could do the Design Sprint and then switch to the Scrum framework to build this MVP. That would be my recommendation and... yeah, that's it."

3.6.8 Capabilities: General supporting capabilities

Above, we've been discussing product development and management related capabilities, that are or can be supported by various IT industry-standard frameworks. Some of the pain points and important factors were disclosed in this context. However, what stands out as being out of the scope of these frameworks on the one hand, but a very relevant capability, that is not inherent in the contract-driven IT-Service business, is NPD-based marketing and sales.

In the very transparent input from SS, we see that the company is investing heavily in these activities and experiments, in search of a winning strategy: "Well, if we now look at our history, in the past we have mainly done sales through the line management and consultants. Even in our classic segment, where we have to adapt, we have increased our sales capacity by 500%. Knowing that this is also a process. Nevertheless, you have to do it, and it is no longer the classic sales, which maybe just means making a phone call or knocking on the door, but we have to combine the different mechanisms well. Whether it is social media campaigns, whether it is telesales, whether it is some kind of contact management mechanism and so on and so forth. I think we have to do a lot of webinars, lectures, networking events, etc. We have to combine a lot of things. And I think we have to try them out. And also constantly adapt, adjust. And to do that, we probably need one or two specialists who just know the mechanisms, and then we need a product owner or somebody who has the courage to take care of the product, to push it forward".

This last point is what is most common in the other companies interviewed, in that the product owner is central to marketing and sales activities and relies heavily on networking: "Someone of us also does a lot of networking, especially in this area of sustainability, we have practically no classical marketing in this sense anymore", - says SK.

"Where we were relatively well positioned was the sales aspect. I think we benefited a lot from the fact that we put our developers directly into sales, because they brought this enthusiasm for the product with them. Authenticity and conviction opened a lot of doors for us," adds BS.

However, this strategy can be difficult to implement when the company is very small and the product owner is also the product developer and main support specialist. MR explains that they tried an external agency for these activities, but with not much success: "The results were also bad externally, and internally people just don't want to

do it. Especially the topic of marketing or something like that, that is simply the important point, I would say, in any case, yes, of course. Also sales and marketing, because we are not so strong in that area“.

The company of MR found a workaround by pushing on the search engine optimization (SEO) for their website and providing a free to use version of their products with limited functionality: "It's available in a stripped-down version. This has the advantage that you are developing the product and it also a kind of marketing. People are looking for something like that on the Internet, and they come to our site. And then naturally the big question is, and that is now the next step, anyways in the next one to two years, that we develop a strategy, how we can now practically bring these customers to also look at our beta product. We actually have a large address base of course over the free version".

Nevertheless, exactly this task of following-up on the trials of the free version, this getting advantage of the user base, would eventually fall into the arms of the product owner in this or that way. So, again, networking in terms of getting in contact with people in the business domain, where one is also an expert.

In a sense, these marketing and sales activities, led by the company's own people with domain knowledge and network, "close the loop". As can be seen from OD's input, who runs a company with a product-based core business, networking is the source of both the revenue from sales and the ideas for new products and partnerships: "On the one hand, of course, we are active in normal sales, also in the area of "cold calling". But a very important sales channel is of course the network. If you have been in business for a long time, you know a lot of customers, you know a lot of partners, and you come across them again and again. That is also a mixture of consistent approach and luck. If that is the case, then you have to say quite clearly that if you simply know a lot of people and have worked with a lot of companies, then one day someone comes around the corner with some ideas, and the word gets around, or from this network you naturally have access to a lot of potential customers where you would otherwise not get anywhere".

4 Analysis and outcomes

Starting this master thesis, we expected to be able to answer two key research questions with the help of literature research and expert interviews. Namely, what are the key relevant factors and capabilities to consider and how to tailor the industry standard frameworks to achieve better and sustainable results in NPD-based BMI at the companies of the selected market segment. And, despite the limitations of the used methods and the format of the master thesis, we managed to get important insights and determine some of the key relevant patterns.

4.1.1 Factors to consider

4.1.1.1 Market segments

Discussing the market situation, as seen from the perspectives of the interviewed companies, we determined, that the macroeconomic downfalls and instability on the German market did not evenly affect the whole German IT service and consulting SME sector. The major factors here are the predominant size/type of the customer companies and the type of services the IT company offers. These are crucial in terms of sensitivity to the macroeconomic fluctuations on the German market (see Fig. 31).

Figure 31. Market segmentation by the prevailing type of customers and the category of provided services

IT-Service companies, focusing on SME segment are generally less affected. Among SMEs, working with the corporate segment, providers of high-tech services and especially in the OEM (e.g. embedded) field are in a better position. The latter are better protected from budget cuts, nearshoring and offshoring.

We do not state that companies, not belonging to the “not affected” segments should not be considering NPD-based BMI. The point here is that companies of the affected segments might consider looking at the other segments as an alternative measure, before or in parallel with innovating their BMs with NPD.

On the other hand, there is a difference in the motivation for the NPD-based BMI for these segments (see Table 3).

Motivation	Affected segment	Not affected segment
Underutilization of resources	An important motivation	-
Stabilization of income	An important motivation	An important motivation
Using an opportunity	Less important	An important motivation
Optimizing the core services	An important motivation	Less important

Table 3. Rationale for NPD-based BMs for segments affected and unaffected by macroeconomic market pressures

4.1.1.2 Investment strategy and idea sourcing

The second factor or rather a combination of factors is related to the investment strategy and the sourcing of the product ideas (see Fig. 32).

Figure 32. Investment strategy, sourcing of the product ideas, sales and marketing

Generally independent of company size, different investment strategies in combination with idea sources and the outcomes for marketing and sales are followed by the IT-service companies of the interviewed group. There are however some reported “golden paths” or successful strategies, offering arguably best combination of minimizing risks while maximizing the chances of success on the market (see Table 4).

Strategy	Comment
1. Stepwise development and use of the products as facilitators of the core services, offered to the regular clients, followed by generalization of the products and their commercialization.	In this case the product development is financed through the regular contracts and validated through the existing customers. A relatively long path, requiring sufficient resources and several relevant projects for the validation and optimization.
2. Product idea comes from a partner, who has the need in this product and is ready to cover part of the product development costs and partner with the IT company in further marketing and sales of the product.	In this case the idea is already pre-validated by the early adopter, who also shares the market risks and facilitates sales and marketing. It needs to be made sure, that the early adopter is also a typical customer for the product and that there is no “obsession with the solution” on the part of the partner. Depending on the case, other market players might be distracted by their competitor co-owning the product.

3. Product idea comes from a partner or a service project with the partner paying for the customized product, but allowing the product to be generalized and owned by the IT-service company.	On the one hand, this scenario minimizes investment and maximizes the potential revenue, but some important advantages of having the customer as a business-partner are lost.
4. IT-Service company has a decent domain knowledge, a network of interested contacts and a domain expert who is capable of driving the product development and sales.	This approach requires resources, available to invest in the product development without an immediate compensation. However, if all the named components are in place, the approach has good chances.

Table 4. Successful idea sourcing and product marketing strategies for the NPD-based BMI

At least within the interviewed group of companies there is no evident correlation between the company size and specialization and the preferred product development strategy. The last of the listed options requires investment resources, so would be less likely to be chosen by the smallest companies. However, even the smallest of the interviewed companies reported situations, when there were “free” product development resources available due to gaps between acquired customer projects. At the same time, each product development path or strategy is realized through its own value stream and required capabilities partially different capabilities, which makes this choice a factor, that needs to be considered in the context of the present master thesis.

4.1.2 Success factors and capabilities

Now let us map the key factors, skills, capabilities and frameworks, named by the interview partners to the capabilities, that we derived from the industry standard frameworks and methodologies in the literature research section.

Important general outcome: in every case we see close connection to the customers and their domain, including communication and networking as a CSF or even the main CSF. This was directly or indirectly named by every interviewed company as such. The corresponding elements are highlighted on the diagrams.

The second dominating CSF is a good gut feeling or “business intuition”, which is however closely related to the first CSF.

4.1.2.1 EAM-related capabilities

EAM-related capabilities. We have not encountered a systematic, framework-based methodological approach to EAM in any of the interviewed companies. The initial BMI decisions were taken rather organically, based on either market pressure, or opening opportunities. In one of the cases a systematic R&D approach came into play (see Fig. 33).

Figure 33. EAM-related capabilities mapping

Market opportunities in this context generally come from close cooperation with the customers, whereby groundbreaking proposals and ideas are shared, needs and requirements understood and transformed in NPD-based BMs.

4.1.2.2 Creation and integration of new BMs, portfolio management

Although in some of the cases tools like Design Thinking and various canvases and the relevant methodologies were mentioned in the context of design and evaluation of product-based BMs, in most cases products are conceived and designed in close collaboration with the customers or partners quite individually. And also in most cases there are no formalized BMs at the starting phase.

Portfolio management is rather considered a “luxury problem”, as most SMEs of the segment either do not have a wide choice of product projects to choose from or this is done by the top or senior management on case-by-case basis (see Fig. 34).

Figure 34. Creation, integration and management of BMs capabilities mapping

As we see here, the key success factors are again domain knowledge and/or good and close contacts and business intuition / gut feeling.

4.1.2.3 Prototyping, MVP development and validation

We encountered the MVP-concept in every interview, although sometimes different terms were used. Agile methodologies, Extreme Programming and a few product management methodologies, such as Lean Startup, Design Sprint and Shape Up were named and are generally either directly used or at least considered (see Fig. 35).

Figure 35. Prototyping, MVP development and validation capabilities mapping

In most cases, where products are developed in direct cooperation with customers or partners, the process does not differ much from the individual agile development of customer owned products.

Accordingly, close and transparent connection with customers and users is also the decisive success factor in this category.

4.1.2.4 Service Management

Service Management was generally regarded as another “luxury problem”, that is expected to be the least of challenges, if a product gets so successful and thousands of customers and users can no longer be individually taken care of by a product expert / product developer / product owner.

In a couple of cases ITSM (ITIL) and DevOps were named as a possible, implicit or real basis. Separately, ensuring information security was named as a CSF by the representative of a major market player (see Fig. 36).

Figure 36. Service management capability mapping

Personal support and close collaboration with the customer were also mentioned as the advantages of custom software development, whereby losing these when switching to e.g. SaaS models was named as a major risk factor by another market player. Thus, even the biggest product developers on the OEM market were reported to provide very individual support and maintain close collaboration, as one of the decisive success factors.

4.1.2.5 Market & Sales

We did not specifically derive marketing and sales capabilities in the overview of the methodologies and frameworks within the literature research section. Of course, these would be part of the target EA, if a framework like TOGAF would be used for the BMI. And Lean Startup is arguably all about marketing and sales. Marketing and sales channels are part of the various BM canvases, used in different frameworks. Lean Startup focuses on traction KPIs. Customer centricity is an element of the SAFe framework. However, there are no specific instructions to be found, how to build or structure these capabilities at a company.

However exactly the capability of marketing and selling own products was named as the most challenging and underdeveloped in the IT service and consulting companies, as this capability differs significantly from the regular IT-Service and Consulting sales. Having this capability can be generally named a CSF anyways. And, again, we see here partnerships, networking and an engaged product owner as the major success factors (see Fig. 37).

Figure 37. Marketing and Sales Mapping

General marketing and sales tools like SEO or limited free versions are also used, of course, as well as cooperation with external marketing and sales agencies. Thus, developing the capability of using these tools is also a success factor, but is largely outside the direct scope of the discussed frameworks.

4.1.3 Capabilities. Maturity levels

Based on the discussion and the above analysis we can draft maturity level assessment for the discussed capabilities and the underlying processes. The assessment is quite subjective and incomplete, as we did not use any quantitative research methodologies or any deeper analysis, so it is to be considered rather as a conceptual exercise or draft for possible further research or EAM.

As discussed in the literature review, we will base our assessment on the CMMI model for the processes, but we will apply it to the aggregated capabilities (see Fig. 38).

Figure 38. Capability Maturity Model Integration® (CMMI)-based process-capability scheme (ISACA, 2018, Objectives, p. 20)

For the purposes of this task, we will categorize the interviewed SMEs in 5 groups (see Table 5):

- A.** Micro- or small companies with more experience in NPD-based business
- B.** Small companies with less experience in NPD-based business
- C.** Midsize company with more experience in NPD-based business
- D.** Midsize company with some experience in NPD-based business
- E.** Midsize company with less experience in NPD-based business

Capability or aggregated capability or category / Group	A	B	C	D	E
Market sensing for possible NPD-based BMs	2	1	4	1	2
Enterprise and organizational agility	1	1	4	2	2
Designing new NPD-based BMs	0-3	1	5	1	2-3
Portfolio management	0	0	5	2	2-3
NPD-project and product management	1-3	1-2	5	2-3	2-3
Service management	1	1	4	2	0
Prototyping / MVP / validated learning	2	1	5	0-2	2-3
NPD-based marketing and sales	2-5	0	5	2	1

Table 5. Capability maturity levels

We see that only group “C”, or rather a specific company in this case, has top maturity levels for almost every relevant capability, based on the responses of its representative. However, it would be wrong to conclude that, that exactly this profile should be considered the target state for every SME of the group. We see that some companies with comparable low levels of maturity for the most capabilities are quite successful in their segments, if other CSFs are there – namely the gut feeling and the close contact with the customers. Nevertheless, our assumption would be that without high maturity levels – 4 or 5 – the company would have limited scaling chances for the NPD-based business.

Confirming this assumption and quantifying it may constitute a subject of future research.

4.1.4 Tailoring the industry standard frameworks

Now we come to the last part of our research subject, namely what hints does our research provide for the tailoring of the industry standard frameworks and methodologies to achieve better and sustainable results in NPD-based BMI at the German IT service and consulting SMEs.

In the previous chapters the following seven frameworks and methodologies were considered: **TOGAF® 10**, **COBIT® 2019**, **SAFe® 6.0**, **PRINCE2® 7**, **Lean Startup**, **Design Sprint** and **ITIL® 4.0**. In the following subsection, we will discuss, how to best tailor them, based on the insights we got from the interviews.

A few more methodologies and frameworks were named on the margins, including Agile (Scrum, Kanban, XP) and DevOps as covering parts of the NPD-based capabilities and tasks. We will not discuss tailoring of these frameworks, as their primary focus in the NPD context is the software engineering process as such,

including “engineering level” project management. There was also a consensus among most of the interviewees, that these methodologies need to be used wherever appropriate with or without modification. However, discussing this in depth is out of scope of the present master thesis.

4.1.4.1 TOGAF

Most of the interviewees were not explicitly asked about TOGAF or ADM, as it was contextually evident, that structured EAM is out of scope for the companies of the given SME size and structure. The upper segment of the group was generally aware of the framework, but referred to internal principles and values, as the basis for EAM, rather than any formalized framework. And this is also in line with the results of a survey conducted on the subject of the adaptation of TOGAF for the SMEs by a group of researchers (Alm & Wißotzki, 2013). And we totally agree with its results: the tasks and considerations, forming the TOGAF’s ADM cycle being generally relevant for any EA change, are relevant for the SMEs, as well.

The interviews on NPD-based BMI at SMEs clearly show, that this BMI implies changes in the business architecture, the information management processes, the technological landscape, to name a few components, that are reflected in the ADM cycle of TOGAF. However, SMEs we interviewed, do not have dedicated enterprise architects, who would be TOGAF-certified and could use the ADM to the full scale. Architectural changes are generally being decided by the top-managers, who are also the owners of their companies.

In other words, applying the ADM cycle at companies of the lower SME segment would basically stop at the Preliminary phase, where the EA capability is assessed. With the higher SME segment it’s different – there, in the context of the NPD-based BMI we found either an established process- and roles-based approach, or the signs of it being gradually established. Arguably, an evolving EAM capability is a success factor in a company’s growth, although that is out of the scope of the present study.

Considering the above, different approaches to TOGAF tailoring could be meaningfully used for the lower and higher segments of the SMEs in question.

The higher SME segment does not appear to have a need for a general company-size-based tailoring of the TOGAF or its ADM, as it can be used directly. Here we rather see a potential benefit in popularizing the method and possibly developing special business training programs for SME top management, that would demonstrate the business-related benefits of a systematic approach to the EAM and would be based

on the real-life examples in the SME domain. There, an NPD-based BMI could be one of the example use cases.

For the lower and middle SME segment, a practical ADM-based guide, specifically tackling the NPD-based BMI could be of value. For example, some of the interviewees in this segment mentioned, having overlooked important processes related to the management of costs and profitability, so they were not established, which resulted in “waste” in the Lean sense. Such a guide could use a limited set of factors and other inputs to consider, given the practically absent EA-capability.

4.1.4.2 COBIT

The author of the present master thesis wants to thank ISACA (formerly known as the Information Systems Audit and Control Association) for providing him with a personal copy of its “COBIT for Small and Medium Enterprises” guide free of charge for the purposes of this work. The name suggests that this is already a tailored version for our target group. However, the definition of the guide’s scope and intended audience practically excludes IT-service SMEs (ISACA, 2018, SMEs, pp. 17), as, depending on the case, one or more of the following criteria are not matched:

- Have limited in-house IT skills and/or capacity
- Do not have a complex IT infrastructure
- Outsource complex tasks
- Aim more to buy (and potentially tailor) tools rather than build them

The other four criteria would be generally relevant, though:

- Have a relatively high risk tolerance, because of their low risk capacity
- Are very cost-conscious
- Have a simple command structure and limited organizational structures in place
- Have a short span of control

To the companies with up to 250 FTEs and that are highly dependent on IT systems and services, the guide recommends using the “top level” framework “COBIT® 2019 Framework: Governance and Management Objectives”.

So, here we have an interesting case. The “top level framework” here is addressed e.g. to the companies with complex IT infrastructure. While IT-service SMEs may use a complex IT infrastructure to provide relevant services to their major customers, this infrastructure may play no or little role in the NPD-based value stream. And the same for other criteria.

The point of the COBIT guide for SMEs is in pre-selecting the prioritized objectives, based on the business and organizational architecture, standard for the SMEs in question. Thus, e.g. within the “Align, Plan and Organize” category, topics related to “Suppliers” are considered very important, while “Innovation” is downprioritized. Depending on the case, for our target group of SMEs this may look exactly opposite. Thus, it would be a challenging, but an interesting and meaningful task to have a COBIT guide, specifically addressing IT-SMEs, building their capabilities for the NPD-based BMs. Popularization and/or rebranding would also be needed, as currently the name COBIT 2019 generally gets heard in this target group as something about the recent pandemic.

4.1.4.3 SAFe

The power of the SAFe (scaled agile) framework is arguably related to the two main aspects of it. On the one hand SAFe combines elements of many of the other referenced frameworks and methodologies, declaring the “lean-agile” approach, as the central one. Thus, Lean, DevOps and Agile (ScrumXP combines Scrum and Extreme Programming) are incorporated in SAFe. And it also includes guidelines for the relevant EAM and service management, although the latter is generally not a focus of the framework. Lean Startup is not explicitly part of the framework, but one can recognize elements of its approach e.g. in Lean Portfolio Management of SAFe.

On the other hand, what makes SAFe stand apart of other industry standard frameworks is exactly the scaling. It is best tailored to suit the needs of large companies. Hence for instance at least some if not all of the major automotive market players in Germany are either already using or actively introducing SAFe, as also confirmed in one of our interviews.

So, what about tailoring SAFe for the SMEs? The combination of the methodologies and frameworks in SAFe as such makes it potentially attractive for the NPD-based BMI at our target group of companies. If not for the scale of it. SAFe is best suited not even for multiple products, but for multiple lines of products and implies an extensive system of roles and processes – the architecture and the resources, that most SMEs have no chance of affording. So, in order to make the framework useful for our subject task and group, it would need to be dramatically downscaled. Although, SAFe would then lose its core focus, given the advantage of combining the other methodologies the way it does and its customer centricity, this could be a meaningful task. Downscaling to cover

working on just a few products. Possibly something for the top part of the SME segment. For those, who would go for it, consider the name dSAFe.

4.1.4.4 PRINCE2, Lean Startup and Design Sprint

One can hardly imagine a “more opposite corners”, where two methodologies / frameworks could come from, that what is the case for PRINCE2 and Lean Startup. PRINCE2 (Projects IN Controlled Environments) comes, at least partially, from the corridors of the UK government, where you would expect them bureaucrats to sit and aim at having more control. So, they got a framework for themselves. The Lean Startup methodology, on the contrary, was developed in Silicon Valley, probably one of the least bureaucratic places one could think of, and from the start was about agility and lean thinking.

Now, when it comes to NPD-based BMI at a private SME, one hardly thinks of PRINCE2 – at least, it was never mentioned by our interview partners. Lean Startup, on the contrary, even if not used in its full scope, is often referred to, while its concept of MVP is in everyone’s blood with almost no exceptions.

And yet, as unexpected, as it may sound, it follows from our research, that exactly the combined strength of both frameworks might suit the NPD-based BMI in the best way. On the one hand, agile is since at least the latest versions (6 and 7) extensively adopted by the PRINCE2 framework, which makes it much more compatible with Lean Startup, than before. On the other hand, robust planning and controlling processes, being arguably the major strength of the framework, are exactly something, that was missing for a few of our interviewees, as they more or less followed the path of validated learning – the Lean Startup way. The bigger the business, the more the controlling side of the NPD-based project management is important, as it is just one of the components of a company’s business, not the core of it.

On the other hand, PRINCE2 is flexible enough to incorporate both the MVP-based product development and the validated learning. The principle of management by exception and the stage management processes give exactly enough space for that, while maintaining control by the project board and the management. The principle of learning from experience and the continuous updating of the business case would also fit. So, that could be a great pair (see Fig. 39).

Figure 39. Combining PRINCE2 and Lean Startup

In this context, wherever applicable, prototyping with Design Sprint could be a stage in the “PRINCE2 – Lean Startup” combined framework, serving as a preparation for the MVP phase, which already requires more investment.

And the “appetite-based” approach of the Shape Up methodology could also be used for defining the project stages, where appropriate.

4.1.4.5 ITIL 4

Service management, and as we are considering digital products, ITSM, was for the most part labelled as a “luxury problem” by the interviewees, representing the lower segment of the SME group. The upper segment named ITIL as a good ITSM basis, but the practical applicability of the framework was made dependent on the maturity of the products, or more exactly the number of customers and users. However, like it is with the MVP concept, components or practices of the ITIL framework, like incident or deployment management to name just two of them, are part of the modern software development industry DNA. The quality and level of implementation varies greatly, of course.

PeopleCert and AXELOS are so far keeping PRINCE2 and ITIL separated, as for PRINCE2 the service management part would already be BAU, business as usual, not covered by the framework. Lean Startup does not focus on the ITSM either, as generally this methodology is not limited to IT or digital products, even if Silicon Valley and Startups are widely associated with these. Hence, if one would think of a combined framework, based on PRINCE2, Lean Startup and Design Sprint specifically for the digital products – and that would be exactly something for the target SME group of the

present work, incorporating the basics of ITIL4 or at least widely referencing it would be meaningful.

Another approach would be to compose a guide on gradually building an ITIL-based ITSM structure around a newly developed product at an SME. This could start at the level of one-man-show, when the product is supported by just one person and all the way up to the creation of a full-scale service around it.

5 Further research

In the present master thesis we used a qualitative methodology to analyze the market and the NPD-based BMI at the German IT service and consulting SMEs. And, although the outcomes appear to be good based, a quantitative study could help confirming the results of the qualitative study.

The other line of work could be a more detailed research on the suggested tailoring of the relevant frameworks, or possibly considering other frameworks and methodologies in this context.

6 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The present master thesis supports the following SDGs:

#8: Decent work and economic growth:

The master thesis is targeted at facilitating sustainable development of the SMEs through a structured and balanced approach to innovation. The sustainable development of the SME sector of the national economy, especially in its high-tech sector, is a key factor in ensuring the sustainable development of the whole EU, promoting competition and thus building the basis for decent work and economic growth.

#17: Partnerships for the goals:

Development of the IT sector and especially in its SME segment is unthinkable without building partnerships within the economic ecosystem. Every digital product is a result of collaboration of numerous co-creators and service providers. The modest scientific contribution of this master thesis consists in drafting a way for the improvement of IT-management and thus to the value co-creation through partnership and collaboration.

7 Literature

1. Charlie Rose (Director). (2014, October 22). Steve Ballmer on His Biggest Regret (Oct. 21, 2014) | Charlie Rose.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v9d3wp2sGPI>
2. Randewich, N. (2024, January 29). Investors see Microsoft's stock market value leaving Apple behind. Reuters.
<https://www.reuters.com/technology/investors-see-microsofts-stock-market-value-leaving-apple-behind-2024-01-29/>
3. Viki, T., Toma, D., & Gons, E. (2019). *The Corporate Startup: How established companies can develop successful innovation ecosystems* (English Edition) (S.14). Management Impact Publishing. Kindle-Version.
4. Mitchell, D. W., & Bruckner Coles, C. (2004). Business model innovation breakthrough moves. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 25(1), 16–26.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02756660410515976>
5. Idrees, H., Xu, J., Haider, S. A., & Tehseen, S. (2023). A systematic review of knowledge management and new product development projects: Trends, issues, and challenges. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 8(2), 100350.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2023.100350>
6. Cooper, R. G. (2019). The drivers of success in new-product development. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 76, 36–47.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2018.07.005>
7. Berends, H., Jelinek, M., Reymen, I., & Stultiëns, R. (2014). Product Innovation Processes in Small Firms: Combining Entrepreneurial Effectuation and Managerial Causation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(3), 616–635. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12117>
8. Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis). (2023, March 25). Erzeugerpreise für Dienstleistungen im Jahr 2022 um 5,5 % gegenüber 2021 gestiegen. Statistisches Bundesamt.
https://www.destatis.de/DE/Presse/Pressemitteilungen/2023/03/PD23_113_61_311.html
9. Felser, K., & Wynn, M. (2023). Managing the Knowledge Deficit in the German Automotive Industry. *Knowledge*, 3(2), 180–195.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/knowledge3020013>

10. Erdiaw-Kwasie, M. O., Abunyewah, M., Yusif, S., & Arhin, P. (2023). Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in a pandemic: A systematic review of pandemic risk impacts, coping strategies and resilience. *Heliyon*, 9(10), e20352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20352>
11. Iqbal, M., & Suzianti, A. (2021). New Product Development Process Design for Small and Medium Enterprises: A Systematic Literature Review from the Perspective of Open Innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(2), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7020153>
12. Mayer, H. O. (2012). Interview und schriftliche Befragung: Grundlagen und Methoden empirischer Sozialforschung: Grundlagen und Methoden empirischer Sozialforschung (6., überarb. edition). Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag.
13. Döring, N., & Bortz, J. (2016). *Forschungsmethoden und Evaluation in den Sozial- und Humanwissenschaften*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41089-5>
14. Wilde, T., & Hess, T. (2007). Forschungsmethoden der Wirtschaftsinformatik. *WIRTSCHAFTSINFORMATIK*, 49 (2007)(4), 280–287. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11576-007-0064-z>
15. European Commission. (2003). *Commission recommendation of 6 May 2003 concerning the definition of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises* (Document number C(2003) 1422). Official Journal of the European Union. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32003H0361&from=EN>
16. Zott, C., Amit, R., & Massa, L. (2011). The Business Model: Recent Developments and Future Research. *Journal of Management*, 37(4), 1019–1042. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206311406265>
17. Klačmer Čalopa, M., Kokot, K., & Đunđek Kokotec, I. (2020). Level of Knowledge and Implementation of Lean Methodology in Small and Medium-sized Croatian Companies. *TEM Journal*, 276–285. <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM91-38>
18. Maurya, A. (2022). *Running Lean* (English Edition). O'Reilly Media. Kindle-Version.

19. Mitchell, D. W., & Bruckner Coles, C. (2004). Business model innovation breakthrough moves. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 25(1), 16–26.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02756660410515976>
20. Teece, D. J. (2010). Business Models, Business Strategy and Innovation. *Long Range Planning*, 43(2–3), 172–194.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2009.07.003>
21. Wirtz, B. W., Pistoia, A., Ullrich, S., & Göttel, V. (2016). Business Models: Origin, Development and Future Research Perspectives. *Long Range Planning*, 49(1), 36–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2015.04.001>
22. Ries, E. (2011). *The Lean Startup: How Today's Entrepreneurs Use Continuous Innovation to Create Radically Successful Businesses* (1st ed., English Edition). Crown Currency. Kindle version.
23. Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers*. John Wiley & Sons.
24. PeopleCert. (2023). PRINCE2® 7—Managing Successful Projects. PeopleCert. E-Book Version.
25. Johanes, F., & Arviansyah, A. (2021). Improving Project Performance: A Review of Business Cases Utilization. Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Sustainable Management and Innovation, ICoSMI 2020, 14-16 September 2020, Bogor, West Java, Indonesia. 1st International Conference on Sustainable Management and Innovation, ICoSMI 2020, 14-16 September 2020, Bogor, West Java, Indonesia, Bogor, Indonesia.
<https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.14-9-2020.2304479>
26. Syamfithriani, T. S., Wibisono, Y., Munir, M., Wibowo, L. A., & Rahayu, A. (2024). Systematic Literature Review: The Role of Enterprise Architecture in Digital Transformation in the Era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. In R. Hurriyati, L. A. Wibowo, S. Sulastri, & L. Lisnawati (Hrsg.), Proceedings of the 8th Global Conference on Business, Management, and Entrepreneurship (GCBME 2023) (Bd. 288, S. 418–425). Atlantis Press International BV.
https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-443-3_55
27. The Open Group. (2022a). TOGAF® Series Guide: Business Modeling. Retrieved May 25, 2024, from https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/business-architecture/business-models.html#_Toc516818729

28. Hermawan, R. A., & Sumitra, I. D. (2019). Designing Enterprise Architecture Using TOGAF Architecture Development Method. IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 662(4), 042021.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/662/4/042021>
29. ISACA. (2018). COBIT® 2019 Framework: Governance and Management Objectives. ISACA, ISBN 978-1-60420-764-4
30. The Open Group. (2022b). TOGAF® Series Guide: Business Capabilities Guide V2. <https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/business-architecture/business-capabilities.html>
31. The Open Group. (2023c). ArchiMate® 3.2 Specification.
<https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate3-doc/ch-Stakeholders-Architecture-Views-and-Viewpoints.html>
32. Boer, H., & During, W. E. (2001). Innovation, what innovation? A comparison between product, process and organisational innovation. International Journal of Technology Management, 22(1/2/3), 83.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTM.2001.002956>
33. European Commission. (2024, May 15). Skills & competences | ESCO v1.2.0.
https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification/skill_main
34. Auth, G., & Jokisch, O. (2023). A systematic mapping study of standards and frameworks for information management in the digital era. Online Journal of Applied Knowledge Management, 11(1), 1–13.
[https://doi.org/10.36965/OJAKM.2023.11\(1\)1-13](https://doi.org/10.36965/OJAKM.2023.11(1)1-13)
35. ISACA. (2021). COBIT for Small and Medium Enterprises. (Guide), ISACA, ISBN 978-1-60420-899-3
36. ISACA. (2018). COBIT® 2019 Framework: Introduction and Methodology. ISACA, ISBN 978-1-60420-763-7
37. Axelos Ltd. (2021). ITIL foundation: ITIL 4 edition (eBook Edition).
PEOPLECERT INTERNATIONAL LTD
38. Yu, Q., Zhao, N., Li, M., Li, Z., Wang, H., Zhang, W., Sui, K., & Pei, D. (2024). A survey on intelligent management of alerts and incidents in IT services. Journal of Network and Computer Applications, 224, 103842.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inca.2024.103842>

39. Desyllas, P., Salter, A., & Alexy, O. (2022). The breadth of business model reconfiguration and firm performance. *Strategic Organization*, 20(2), 231–269. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476127020955138>
40. Ramdani, B., Binsaif, A., & Boukrami, E. (2019). Business model innovation: A review and research agenda. *New England Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 22(2), 89–108. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NEJE-06-2019-0030>
41. Womack, J. P., Jones, D. T., Roos, D., & Technology, M. I. of. (1990). *Machine that Changed the World*. Simon and Schuster.
42. Agile Alliance. (2001). Manifesto for Agile Software Development. Retrieved from <http://agilemanifesto.org/>
43. Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509–533. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199708\)18:7<509::AID-SMJ882>3.0.CO;2-Z](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199708)18:7<509::AID-SMJ882>3.0.CO;2-Z)
44. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 12, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com>
45. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Business Agility. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 14, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/business-agility/>
46. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Organizational Agility. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 15, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/organizational-agility/>
47. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). System Architect. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 16, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/system-architect>
48. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Enterprise Architect. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 16, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/enterprise-architect>
49. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Portfolio Vision. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 17, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/portfolio-vision/>
50. Scaled Agile Inc. (2023). Lean Portfolio Management. Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe) 6.0. Scaled Agile Framework. Retrieved June 18, 2024, from <https://scaledagileframework.com/lean-portfolio-management/>

51. The Open Group. (2022). TOGAF Series Guide: Maturity Models. https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/architecture-maturity-models/index.html#_Toc95289664
52. The Open Group. (2022). The TOGAF® Standard, 10th Edition, Digital Edition. <https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/>
53. The Open Group. (2022). The TOGAF® Leader's Guide to Establishing and Evolving an EA Capability. https://pubs.opengroup.org/togaf-standard/togaf-leaders-guide/togaf-leaders-guide_10.html
54. Ries, E. (2017). *The Startup Way: How Entrepreneurial Management Transforms Culture and Drives Growth* (English Edition). Penguin Books Ltd. Kindle-Version.
55. Shepherd, D. A., & Gruber, M. (2021). The Lean Startup Framework: Closing the Academic–Practitioner Divide. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 45(5), 967–998. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1042258719899415>
56. Gadatsch, A., & Mayer, E. (2013). *Masterkurs IT-Controlling: Grundlagen und Praxis für IT-Controller und CIOs - Balanced Scorecard - Portfoliomanagement - Wertbeitrag der IT - Projektcontrolling ... - IT-Kosten- und Leistungsrechnung* (5th edition, Kindle edition). Springer Vieweg.
57. Singer, R. (n.d.). *Shape Up: Stop Running in Circles and Ship Work that Matters*. Retrieved August 8, 2024, from <https://basecamp.com/shapeup>
58. Knapp, J., Zeratsky, J., & Kowitz, B. (2016). *Sprint: The bestselling guide to solving business problems and testing new ideas the Silicon Valley way* (1. Aufl.). Transworld Digital.
59. Alm, R., & Wißotzki, M. (2013). TOGAF Adaption for Small and Medium Enterprises. In W. Abramowicz (Hrsg.), *Business Information Systems Workshops* (Bd. 160, S. 112–123). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41687-3_12

8 Expert Interviews (Attachments)

1. Interview with “BS”, Consultant, and “AW”, Senior Consultant, medium-sized IT service provider, Baden-Württemberg
2. Interview with “FS”, Managing Director, small IT service provider, Hamburg
3. Interview with “JK”, Product and Project Manager, major customer, Baden-Württemberg
4. Interview with “MR”, Managing Director, small IT service provider, Baden-Württemberg
5. Interview with “OD”, Managing Director, small IT service provider, Schleswig-Holstein
6. Interview with “SK”, senior manager, small IT service provider, Saxony
7. Interview with “SS”, management, medium-sized IT service provider, Baden-Württemberg
8. Interview with “TN”, business consultant, self-employed and small IT service provider, Hamburg
9. Interview with “VKN”, product and project manager, key account, Baden-Württemberg
10. Interview with “DFB”, senior manager, medium-sized IT service provider, North Rhine-Westphalia

9 Use of AI-based tools

Nowadays, if something is written in a digital form, one can never exclude that AI based tools were involved. I am writing these lines in a **Microsoft Office 365 Word** application, which is currently relying on AI-based algorithms, e.g. for active word- and sentence completion, grammar and style checks, etc. The operating system (OS) that I am using is **Microsoft Windows 11**, currently on a **Microsoft Surface Pro 9 laptop** – I'm sure both the OS and the lower-level programmatic components of the laptop environment are massively using algorithms, that would be arguably classified as AI. Right now, and quite often I'm also listening to electronic **music, streaming** from web-based platforms **PromoDj** and **Deezer** – it helps me to focus, but I'm sure AI-based tools were used for the creation of the music and on the streaming website. The **active noise canceling** algorithm in my headset might use AI as well, not sure.

I used **ChatGPT 4o** LLM with web interface and my personal Plus subscription, while building a list of companies to interview for this master thesis, based on the criteria I entered as prompts. The list was further refined by me via web search with **Google Search** and **Google Chrome browser** – I'm sure both are massively using AI algorithms. Then I was looking for the relevant employees of these companies on the **LinkedIn** platform and contacting them via my **LinkedIn business account** and **InMail** and **Microsoft Outlook** – these tools are using AI-algorithms for sure. Some emails and messages were written with the help of **ChatGPT** and **DeepL/DeepL Write**. I also used both **ChatGPT** and **Google Search** to navigate through some of the web-based resources and search for references to some of my ideas relevant to this master thesis. **Amazon Kindle** Windows App and **Adobe Acrobat** were used to read sources. I used **DALL-E** AI-based drawing engine to draw the yin-yang basis of the Figure 39. I used **DeepL** and **DeepL Write** Windows Apps with my premium account for translations, grammar and style improvement.

For the transcription of the recorded interviews I used my premium **Unifire.ai** account with the data protection agreement and **Microsoft Teams** transcription.

Having named all the above tools and considering there could be further underlying tools I am not aware of or unintentionally missed here, I hereby guarantee that I am the author of all text and illustrations in this master's thesis that are not directly referenced as taken from other sources, and I take full responsibility for the content of this work.